

Teaching at the Low Level

Evidence on Direct Effects, Spillovers, and Parental Engagement in Remedial Education in El Salvador^{*}

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When classroom instruction is locked to the curriculum and home support is limited, students with accumulated learning deficits face near-zero marginal returns to instruction. We study two remedial literacy interventions in rural El Salvador using an RCT that randomizes 606 households (with \geq one low-performing student) from 26 schools to: (i) five months of twice-weekly, 90-minute small-group pull-out sessions during school hours, or (ii) the same sessions plus a low-cost parental engagement component (WhatsApp messages and three focus meetings), versus control. We estimate small treatment–control differences in literacy endline scores, but these are masked by sizable within-school spillovers: the average control student (22.7% treated peers) gains 0.10–0.14 SD, while the average treated student gains 0.20–0.25 SD relative to low-exposure controls. The parent add-on yields no additional gains and does not increase measured parental engagement. Evidence suggests scope for further gains through higher realized treatment exposure, improved targeting, and more intensive parent-facing designs that translate information into sustained at-home practice.

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1 Introduction

Despite impressive gains in school enrollment over recent decades, many low- and middle-income countries still struggle to translate educational investments into human capital. The contrast with high-income countries is stark: only 25 percent of primary students in developing countries reach intermediate learning benchmarks, compared to 66 percent in developed countries (Altinok et al., 2018). In literacy, this gap implies that by the end of fourth grade, 75 percent of students in low- and middle-income countries are unable to locate information in a text or draw simple inferences about meaning or characters (Altinok et al., 2018). These disparities matter because evidence indicates that learning achievements, rather than enrollment alone, are what drives economic development (Angrist et al., 2021; Hanushek and Woessmann, 2012a,b; Hanushek, 2013).

At the *classroom level*, learning is often constrained by two interrelated challenges that limit effective instruction (Pritchett and Beatty, 2015). First, many students fall behind early, and learning gaps widen substantially over time. Second, teachers operate within highly structured systems characterized by rigid curricula, limited autonomy, and pressure to cover grade-level content at a pace most students cannot absorb (Coccia et al., 2026). Together, these constraints produce classrooms in which the pace and content of instruction are systematically misaligned with students' actual learning levels (Pritchett and Beatty, 2015). As a result, especially for lower-performing students, the marginal returns to additional instruction in such classrooms are close to zero (Banerjee et al., 2016; Patel and Sandefur, 2020).

However, learning deficits are shaped not only by classroom instruction but also by the environments in which children practice and reinforce new skills. For foundational competencies such as literacy, learning also depends on repetition, reinforcement, and use outside the classroom, particularly through practice at *home* (Angrist et al., 2022). Yet, similar to classrooms, coordination frictions also emerge at home: parents often have limited information about their child's learning level or about how to effectively support skill development at home (e.g., Dizon-Ross, 2019; Bettinger et al., 2021; Angrist et al., 2022). As a result, even when instruction is adjusted to students' needs, opportunities to reinforce learning outside the classroom are not always fully realized.

In response to these classroom- and household-level constraints, we evaluate two remedial literacy interventions aimed at closing foundational literacy gaps for low-performing students in rural El Salvador, implemented through a randomized con-

trolled trial (RCT). We randomly assign 606 households (containing at least one low-performing student) from 26 schools across grades two to nine to one of three groups: (i) five months of twice-weekly, remedial pull-out sessions delivered in small groups of 10 to 15 students and targeting foundational literacy skills for 90 minutes during school hours; (ii) the same remedial literacy sessions complemented by a parental engagement component, consisting of twice-weekly WhatsApp messages as well as three parent focus meetings designed to encourage student motivation and learning support; or (iii) a control group that receives neither pull-out remedial instruction nor the parental engagement component. The study sample explicitly targets all students from grade two to grade nine identified as struggling readers and writers by their teachers using a simple classification rule, complemented by test-based trimming (exclude top 15%).

Our analysis is pre-specified and draws on four complementary data sources. First, we administer comprehensive student assessments at baseline (two months prior to implementation) and endline (immediately after program completion), which constitute our main outcomes and capture a broad range of foundational literacy skills, alongside student background characteristics and non-cognitive outcomes. Our primary literacy outcome is a weighted aggregate score; we assess robustness using an alternative measure based on Item Response Theory (IRT) and examine effects across nine pre-specified literacy subconcepts (e.g., reading, reading comprehension, and writing). Second, we collect administrative school grades at baseline and endline to benchmark learning gains against language grades and assess spillovers to other subjects. Third, to measure implementation fidelity and compliance, we assemble detailed participation data for students and parents, including high-frequency measures of parental engagement with intervention messages (e.g., receipt, reading, reactions, and responses). Fourth, we complement these quantitative data with semi-structured teacher interviews to inform the interpretation of mechanisms.

Across both treatment arms, we observe small positive differences in literacy outcomes relative to students assigned to the control group. Students offered remedial literacy sessions score approximately 0.06 standard deviations higher on both weighted percent-correct test scores and IRT-based measures, though these differences are not statistically significant ($p = 0.20$). Adding a parental engagement component yields slightly smaller differences—0.04 standard deviations for weighted percent-correct scores ($p = 0.35$) and 0.02 standard deviations for IRT scores ($p = 0.64$). We cannot reject equality between the two treatment arms ($0.43 \leq p \leq 0.85$). These magnitudes are consistent with ex ante power calculations, which indicate that the study is un-

derpowered to detect effects smaller than 0.19 standard deviations at conventional significance levels.

Analyzing mechanisms reveals the presence of non-negligible within-school spillovers. We find that students assigned to the control group perform better in classrooms with a higher share of treated peers. This pattern is consistent across three main outcome measures—weighted literacy scores, IRT-based scores, and language grades—with positive and predominantly statistically significant differences at higher exposure levels relative to low exposure, and is not driven by class size or average class ability. The average control student is exposed to 22.7 percent (≈ 4) treated students in their class which corresponds to average estimated spillovers to the control group of 0.10–0.14 standard deviations ($0.04 \leq p \leq 0.25$ depending on outcome measure). Consistent with these patterns, comparisons between treated and control students in low-exposure classrooms reveal differences of approximately 0.16–0.24 standard deviations, statistically significant for all three outcome measures (weighted score $p = 0.08$; IRT score $p = 0.03$; language grades $p = 0.07$). By contrast, outcomes for treated students exhibit little systematic variation with peer treatment exposure, providing limited evidence of additional spillovers operating among treated students themselves. Together, these findings suggest that spillovers to untreated peers are economically meaningful and may attenuate intent-to-treat differences.

While the intervention generates meaningful learning gains once spillovers are taken into account, estimated effects remain smaller than impacts reported for the most successful remedial programs, which reach up to 0.7 standard deviations (Banerjee et al., 2016). We discuss several features of the implementation that help contextualize this difference. First, administrative delays reduced implementation intensity to 30–35 sessions instead of the planned 40, and regular attendance was modest: fewer than half of treated students attended at least 75 percent of sessions. Consistent with this, treatment-on-the-treated estimates are roughly twice as large as intent-to-treat estimates. Second, to benchmark our setting directly against successful Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) remedial programs, that group students according to their skill level, we map students’ baseline literacy skills into the learning-level classification used in Banerjee et al. (2016). Despite explicitly targeting low-performing students, this exercise reveals substantially greater heterogeneity in baseline skills in our sample than in TaRL settings where students are not pre-selected. This complicates aligning instructional content with students’ learning levels. Finally, we find no evidence that augmenting remedial instruction with a parental component improves literacy outcomes, even after accounting for spillovers. Although message receipt was high,

parental responses and sustained engagement were limited, suggesting that informational inputs alone were insufficient to translate into meaningful learning support at home.

This study contributes to four strands of literature. First, we add to the literature on remedial education. Much of the existing evidence focuses on interventions delivered through teachers (Chimbutane et al., 2026; Duflo et al., 2020; Dixon et al., 2011; Banerjee et al., 2016) or after-school programs (Banerjee et al., 2010; Saavedra et al., 2019). Despite several influential studies in the field (e.g., Duflo et al., 2011; Banerjee et al., 2016, 2007), there is relatively little evidence on pull-out, targeted remediation delivered during the school day, particularly when implemented schoolwide across multiple grades. It thus remains unclear whether remediation in potentially more heterogeneous, cross-grade settings is as effective as grade-specific targeting (Cabezas et al., 2021; Marinelli et al., 2024). However, designating an extra instructor to low-performing students may be a promising approach in settings where teachers are constrained by curricula, even as deficits in basic skills such as reading and writing persist into higher grades and dampen learning in other subjects. This model mirrors common programs in high-income countries (such as reading specialists in the U.S.) and we show that it also holds promise in low-income contexts under effective program delivery.

Second, we contribute to the mixed literature on parental engagement in education by studying a setting where low-cost parental involvement is explicitly layered onto a school-based remedial intervention. Existing evidence shows that light-touch parental engagement interventions, usually delivered via SMS or phone calls, can affect parental beliefs, home investments as well as learning outcomes (Dizon-Ross, 2019; Bettinger et al., 2021; Angrist et al., 2022; Hernández-Agramonte et al., 2022; Kigobe et al., 2021). Yet, these interventions often operate in isolation from classroom instruction and exhibit substantial heterogeneity by parental education, stress, student baseline skills or absenteeism (Aurino and Wolf, 2024; Amaral et al., 2024; Cortes et al., 2021; Mateo Díaz et al., 2020; Banerji et al., 2013). Our design tests whether parental engagement works when it builds on in-school remediation that relaxes classroom constraints, allowing us to assess the added value of parental involvement once students are on a more appropriate learning path.

Third, we extend the literature on spillovers (e.g. Miguel and Kremer, 2004; Angelucci and De Giorgi, 2009; Bobonis and Finan, 2009; Büchel et al., 2022). Most education evaluations randomize at the school level to avoid within-school interference (Banerjee et al., 2007; Duflo et al., 2011; Saavedra et al., 2019; Berlinski et al.,

2023). In our setting, budgetary and logistical constraints require individual-level assignment, implying a trade-off between feasibility and statistical power on the one hand, and potential spillovers on the other. The spillovers we report in this study are informative about the consequences of imperfect targeting in remedial education programs. In practice, policymakers allocate remedial support under administrative and budget constraints using noisy measures of achievement. The finding that untreated low-performing students experience sizable gains implies that the welfare loss from excluding some eligible students is smaller than would be implied by treated-only effects. Such indirect effects are difficult to identify in school-level evaluations where all (eligible) students within a school usually receive treatment, but are directly relevant for assessing the cost-effectiveness and practical implementation of remediation policies.

Fourth and last, we add to an emerging literature on replication (Angrist et al., 2023) and implementation (Angrist et al., 2025) of existing approaches, with the goals of strengthening external validity and maximizing program impact. While most evidence on remedial education comes from India and Sub-Saharan Africa, we study implementation in Latin America. We also adopt a policy-realistic design in which students are assigned through teacher nomination, mirroring how remediation would typically be allocated in practice. Results indicate that this assignment process may complicate targeting and lead to greater heterogeneity within remedial groups.

2 Study Design

2.1 Context and Interventions

The study was conducted in public schools in the department of Morazán, a predominantly rural and economically disadvantaged region of El Salvador (see Figure 1). Teachers in Morazán face a dual challenge: many students exhibit substantial learning deficits even in higher grades, while instruction is governed by a rigid, centrally prescribed curriculum that leaves little scope for instructional differentiation and support of left-behind students (Coccia et al., 2026). This combination creates a setting in which, particularly for low-performing students, additional instruction translate into minimal learning gains.

At the same time, low-performing students not only fail to receive adequate, targeted support from teachers but also face limited instructional support at home. For foundational competencies such as literacy, learning depends critically on repetition,

reinforcement, and practice outside the classroom (e.g., Angrist et al., 2022). Yet anecdotal evidence from our setting suggests that many parents view education as the sole responsibility of teachers.

In response to these classroom and household challenges, we evaluate two interventions aimed at closing foundational literacy gaps for low-performing students. Interventions are implemented over a five-month period between March and October 2025 (see timeline in Figure 2 in Section 2.3). They target students from grades two to nine and are designed to provide structured catch-up opportunities during regular school hours.²

Treatment 1: Remedial Literacy Workshops. Students assigned to the first treatment receive twice-weekly remedial literacy classes in small groups of 10 to 15 students (formed across grades). Each session lasts 90 minutes and takes place during regular school hours. The program had a total duration of 4.5 months with 30-35 sessions being implemented.³ Instruction is delivered by external facilitators hired and trained by the local Swiss-Salvadorian NGO Consciente. Materials were developed by educational experts from Consciente and target foundational reading and writing skills. For a full review of existing evidence on interventions in low- and middle-income countries involving remedial instruction, see Table A13.

Treatment 2: Remedial Literacy Workshops with Parental Engagement. The second treatment arm builds on the remedial classes described above and adds a parental engagement component. Parents receive two motivational WhatsApp messages per week encouraging them to support their child’s learning through simple literacy-related activities at home. Approximately half of the messages were delivered through parent Whatsapp group chats and the remainder through individual chats. Each week included one message focused on motivation and one practice-oriented message covering oral language, writing, and reading. Table A12 provides a summary of the messages. In addition, three parent focus meetings are held over the course of the intervention period. These meetings aim to raise awareness of children’s learning needs and promote parental involvement in education. For a full review of existing evidence on interventions in low- and middle-income countries involving parents in education, see Table A14.

²In practice, the majority of students (98.3 percent) are in grades 2 to 6.

³Some sessions were occasionally displaced by school-specific activities—some mandated by the Ministry— and it was not always feasible to reschedule them.

Figure 1: Study Location

Notes: Panel (a) shows a map of El Salvador with the department of Morazán highlighted. Panel (b) shows a map of Morazán with the locations of participating schools.

Control group: Students in the control group continue with regular classroom instruction and do not receive any remedial support during the study period.

2.2 Sampling and Randomization

From the universe of 331 schools in Morazán, we excluded schools for one of two reasons. First, we removed schools from the sample due to logistical constraints, including small schools (less than approximately 20 students, as reported by school directors) and remote schools. Second, to avoid overlap with pre-existing instructional support, we discarded schools that employed a government-appointed inclusion support teacher (DAI) responsible for assisting students with learning difficulties and promoting inclusive education. Such schools constitute the majority in Morazán, resulting in a final sample of 26 schools.

Table A1 compares schools in the experimental sample to the average school in Morazán and to national averages. The average sample school is rural, enrolls 163 primary students with nine corresponding teachers, operates both morning and afternoon shifts, does not offer secondary grades, and achieves a score of 50% on a national standardized assessment (comparable to the national mean). Consistent with the sampling criteria, sample schools enroll substantially more primary students (nearly twice as many) and employ more teachers than other schools in Morazán, accompanied by a higher prevalence of afternoon shifts. Sample schools are less likely to offer secondary grades, and standardized test scores are modestly lower than those of other schools

in the department.

Upon school selection, we conducted baseline assessments with students identified by their teachers as struggling with reading and writing.⁴ This emulates a practical, real-world policy, where teachers determine what students are in need of remedial education. To reduce the risk of misidentification by teachers and ensure the intervention targeted the most relevant group, we excluded the top 15% of students based on their baseline literacy scores. This threshold was chosen as a trade-off between statistical power and the need to focus on low-performing students that can benefit from a targeted intervention. This results in a final sample of 663 students from 606 households and 26 schools. Assuming conservatively, that baseline covariates explain 50% of the variance⁵, the study is powered to detect an effect size of 0.19 standard deviations with 80% power at the 5% significance level, both when comparing each treatment group to the control group and when comparing the two treatment groups to each other.

To avoid spillovers between siblings, randomization was conducted at the household level. Since most students do not have a sibling in the sample (mean: 1.1 students per household), the majority of households consists of one student. Due to budgetary constraints, randomization at the school level was not feasible. Although we did not expect substantial within-school spillovers relative to the main intervention effects, our estimates represent a lower bound of treatment effects. We assess the implications of household-level randomization for internal validity in Section 4.1.

We stratify by school as well as below- or above-median performance within schools in the baseline exam. With 26 schools, this results in 52 strata. Randomization is carried out in four rounds: First, assignments are made within each stratum. Second, any remaining unassigned households are randomized within schools. Third, if some households are still unassigned, they are randomized within overall below- and above-median performing households. Finally, any leftover households are assigned completely at random. This procedure resulted in 224 students in treatment 1, 223 students in treatment 2 and 216 students in the control group.

⁴The criteria used to identify struggling students by teachers were difficulty reading a short paragraph aloud, and/or writing a simple sentence.

⁵This calculation is based on data from two previous trials run by the research team in El Salvador, which found the explanatory power of age, sex, cohort and baseline test to be 0.45 and 0.69 respectively (Büchel et al., 2022; Coccia et al., 2026).

2.3 Data

We use four sources of data to analyze study impacts, mechanisms as well as compliance. First and most importantly, we conducted student assessments at baseline, two months before project start, and at endline, immediately after project end (see timeline in Figure 2). Beyond our primary literacy outcomes, exams gathered information on students’ background and a set of non-cognitive outcomes. All tests were double-graded and double-coded to ensure accuracy. Second, complementary to our own assessments, we also obtained school grades at base- and endline. Third, to measure compliance and monitor implementation, we collect program participation and engagement data. Lastly, we complement our quantitative data with qualitative interviews from teachers.

Figure 2: 2025 Project Timeline

Notes: The shaded area shows the intervention’s planned duration. Due to a delay in Ministry of Education (MoE) approval, which was received at the end of May, the intervention started in June.

Assessments comprised 26 main items and lasted approximately 50 minutes. They covered a comprehensive range of literacy skills, including reading, writing, comprehension, fluency, phonological awareness, orthography, grammar and motor skills (for a detailed list of exam items see Appendix A1). To capture multiple dimensions of literacy and to ensure coverage of students with very weak skills, the assessments included both a written ($\sim 2/3$ of the exam) and an oral ($\sim 1/3$ of the exam) component, the latter of which was administered individually by trained enumerators. Although the baseline and endline assessments did not include identical items, item types were largely the same, with only specific components (such as words, pictures, and texts) replaced. Additionally, the endline assessment was slightly adjusted in difficulty to reduce potential ceiling effects arising from student learning over the year.

Our primary literacy outcome is a weighted total score of all literacy-related outcomes. The aggregation and the weights of each of the subitems was pre-registered in a pre-analysis plan. As an alternative measure, we apply Item Response Theory (IRT) to estimate students’ latent abilities θ . We estimate a mixed 2PL/3PL model:

for multiple-choice items or tasks with a high likelihood of guessing (e.g., connecting three words with their corresponding image), the guessing parameter is freely estimated, whereas for all other items it is fixed at zero (2PL). Because IRT assumes conditional independence, we aggregate subitems belonging to the same main task—which likely remain correlated even after conditioning on θ —and construct a binary indicator equal to one if more than 50% of the subitems are answered correctly.⁶

To detect more granular changes in students’ literacy skills, we additionally group items into nine subconcepts: reading, writing, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, fluency, phonological awareness, orthography, grammar and motor skills. Reading and writing are the largest categories, accounting for more than 40 percent of the test, while the smallest categories, orthography, grammar and motor skills, are represented by only one or two items each (see Appendix A1 for a detailed explanation of subconcepts).

In addition to test scores, we also obtain students’ school grades in the four core subjects taught at school: language, math, science and civics values. These allow us to benchmark our effect against general language performance as well as to examine potential spillovers to other subjects. School grades are issued on a tri-trimester basis, where the first trimester maps to our baseline, prior to any intervention, and the last trimester corresponds to our endline.

As secondary outcomes, we measure a set of non-cognitive skills. These include socio-emotional outcomes such as academic self-concept, perseverance and growth mindset and attitudes toward school, as well as number of friends, school-related activities at home and lastly, future aspirations. We also collect data on parental engagement in students’ learning as reported by students. Additional background data on students and households allow for summary statistics, balance checks and heterogeneity analyses by gender, age, baseline performance, socio-economic status and parental support at home.

To track attendance and engagement, we maintain detailed records of student and parent participation in literacy sessions and parent meetings. We also measure parental engagement by recording interactions with messages sent to parents, including whether messages were received, read in group chats, as well as whether parents responded and how.

Lastly, to complement our quantitative measures in exploring mechanisms, we also conduct semi-structured interviews with a randomly chosen subset of six teach-

⁶We estimate the IRT model separately at baseline and endline and do not link the two scales, as the sets of test items are not identical across waves.

ers, stratified by school and grade. Interviews last approximately half an hour and are organized around four main topics: perceived effects of the remedial sessions as well as the parental component, spillovers to control students, and suggestions for improvement.

2.4 Baseline Characteristics and Attrition

Table 1 confirms successful randomization across students. A joint orthogonality test of baseline characteristics indicates that treatment assignment does not jointly predict baseline values; we cannot reject the null of no differences across experimental groups ($p = 0.73$). We also examine overall balance between each experimental group pair separately and fail to reject balance (Control vs. T1 $p = 0.40$; Control vs. T2 $p = 0.77$; T1 vs. T2 $p = 0.65$).

The average student in the sample is approximately 10 years old, male, and scores slightly below 50% on the baseline literacy assessment. Students live in households of about six members, typically with both parents present, and 74% have literate parents. Figure 3 illustrates average student literacy skills from sample items. Performance is highest on basic tasks, with average accuracy above 85% for reading and writing individual letters. Accuracy declines to approximately 70–80% for word reading and sentence-level tasks, and falls below 50% for paragraph-level reading comprehension.

Overall attrition between baseline and endline is limited (14%) and we find no evidence of differential attrition across treatment arms (see Table A2; $p = 0.51$). Balance in the recaptured sample is maintained, with no statistically significant differences across experimental groups (see Tables A3; $p = 0.68$). Although observed attrition does not pose a threat to internal validity, it affects the composition of the analysis sample: students who attrit are older and perform worse at baseline than those who remain in the study (see Table A4; overall balance $p = 0.07$). Consequently, our ITT estimates apply to a selected subpopulation of the originally enrolled students. Because the initial study sample is itself not representative of schools in the department or nationally, this compositional change does not meaningfully alter the external validity of our findings.

Table 1: Balance at Baseline – Entire Sample

	Control	T1: Literacy	T2: Literacy + parents	P-value
Age	10.042 (1.797)	10.080 (1.868)	10.045 (1.765)	0.918
Female	0.347 (0.477)	0.371 (0.484)	0.327 (0.470)	0.521
Baseline score	0.457 (0.229)	0.470 (0.225)	0.460 (0.230)	0.367
Socioeconomic background (PCA)	0.067 (1.474)	-0.035 (1.443)	-0.030 (1.456)	0.664
Household size	5.005 (1.759)	5.398 (2.264)	5.347 (2.013)	0.116
Lives with mother and father	0.560 (0.489)	0.505 (0.490)	0.586 (0.479)	0.218
Mother and father literate	0.702 (0.428)	0.731 (0.417)	0.736 (0.415)	0.757
Likes to go to school	0.939 (0.238)	0.946 (0.226)	0.931 (0.251)	0.748
Orthogonality Tests				
Joint orthogonality test				0.728
Bivariate: Control vs T1				0.398
Bivariate: Control vs T2				0.765
Bivariate: T1 vs T2				0.649

Columns 1-3 show the means of baseline characteristics for the different treatment groups (standard deviations in parentheses). Column 4 reports the p-values for the null hypothesis that treatment status does not predict individual variables, controlling for age, sex, baseline score and stratum fixed effects, except for age (does not include age fixed effects), sex (does not include sex fixed effects) and baseline score (does not include baseline score effects). The joint orthogonality test reports the p-value for the null hypothesis that all baseline variables are jointly uncorrelated with the treatment assignment. The bivariate tests report the p-value for the null hypothesis that the different pairings of treatment groups do not differ on any baseline variable. Orthogonality tests include age, sex, socioeconomic background index (PCA), baseline score, household size, an indicator of whether the child lives with its mother and one of whether it lives with its father, an indicator of whether it likes to go to school, and stratum fixed effects. Missing values of the baseline variables are imputed using the group mean. All standard errors are clustered at the household level. Observations per group: Control = 216; T1: Literacy = 224; T2: Literacy + parents = 223.

3 Results

3.1 Empirical strategy

Empirical strategy was fully specified in a pre-analysis plan. We estimate intent-to-treat effects on endline outcomes Y_{ih} using the following linear regression specification:

$$Y_{ih} = \alpha + \gamma T_h + \beta(A_{ih}, F_{ih}, B_{ih}) + \lambda S_h + \varepsilon_{ih} \quad (1)$$

, where Y_{ih} denotes the endline outcome of student i in household h , T_h contains indicators for the treatment status of household h and vector (A_{ih}, F_{ih}, B_{ih}) includes

Figure 3: Baseline Assessment Descriptives

Notes: The figure shows the average percentage of correct responses across baseline sample items. Error bars indicate standard errors.

student i 's age⁷, an indicator for female, and baseline reading score. The vector S_h denotes strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The coefficients in γ capture intent-to-treat effects relative to the control group.

In the case of subconcepts (e.g. motor skills, writing, reading etc.), we control for the total weighted baseline score instead of subconcept score. For IRT scores and school grades, we use the corresponding baseline values as a control. For non-cognitive outcomes, we do not include a corresponding baseline control as these outcomes were not assessed in the baseline. We additionally examine specifications without covariates.

3.2 Results

Both treatment arms yield small but positive differences in literacy outcomes relative to the control group. Students offered remedial literacy sessions score 0.06 standard deviations higher on both percent-correct test scores and IRT-based measures. However, the estimates falls short of conventional statistical significance ($p = 0.20$). This is consistent with our power calculations, which indicate that the study is not sufficiently powered to reliably detect effects smaller than 0.19 standard deviations at the 5% significance level.

⁷We use age fixed effects, $age > 14$ was binned to preserve statistical power. For the same reason, we do not include grade fixed effects, which we expect to be largely absorbed by age fixed effects.

Table 2: ITT estimates: Main Outcomes

	Endline score	Endline score IRT
Literacy	0.060 (0.048)	0.061 (0.049)
Literacy+ parents	0.051 (0.047)	0.029 (0.049)
Control mean %	0.531	-0.028
N	580	580

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline with complete baseline data is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Augmenting the remedial sessions with a parental component yields slightly smaller intent-to-treat estimates: 0.05 standard deviations for percent-correct scores ($p = 0.28$) and 0.03 standard deviations for IRT scores ($p = 0.55$). Although neither estimate is statistically distinguishable from zero, we also fail to reject the null hypothesis that the estimates of the two treatment arms are equal (weighted score $p = 0.86$; IRT score $p = 0.52$).

Table A5 presents an alternative specification prespecified in the pre-analysis plan that omits controls for sex, age, and baseline score. The resulting estimates corroborate our main findings, producing slightly larger point estimates and marginally stronger statistical significance relative to the controlled specification.

As an additional robustness check, we use school-reported language grades as an alternative outcome measure. These results are broadly consistent, yielding ITT estimates between 0.06 and 0.07 standard deviations across both treatment arms (see Tables A6 and A7). Estimates based on grades are noisier, most likely reflecting the weaker predictive power of baseline grades for endline grades ($R^2 = 0.36$) relative to the predictive power of baseline test scores for endline test scores ($R^2 = 0.77$).⁸

Across all six pre-specified specifications, including test scores, IRT scores, and grades estimated with and without controls, point estimates for both treatments are consistently small but positive. Effect sizes range from 0.03 standard deviations (treatment 2 on IRT scores in the main specification) to 0.12 standard deviations

⁸We find mixed evidence of spillovers to other subjects. While point estimates for math grades are close to zero, estimates for science and civics values grades are only slightly smaller than those for language, though even more imprecise (see Table A6).

(treatment 1 on percent-correct scores in the specification without controls). In none of these cases can we reject the null hypothesis that treatment effects are equal across the two arms ($0.43 \leq p \leq 0.85$).

Table 3 reports ITT estimates for the nine pre-specified subconcepts, including writing, motor skills, reading, reading comprehension, reading fluency, listening comprehension, phonological awareness, orthography, and grammar. Gains in the aggregate literacy score appear to be driven primarily by improvements in writing, with ITT effects of 0.17 and 0.16 standard deviations for treatment 1 and treatment 2, respectively ($p < 0.01$ and $p = 0.01$). In addition, treatment 1 yields positive effects on higher-level reading skills, with estimated impacts of 0.13 standard deviations for reading comprehension ($p = 0.03$) and 0.10 standard deviations for reading fluency ($p = 0.12$).

4 Discussion

The modest magnitude of the intention-to-treat estimates contrasts with the typically larger effects reported in the literature on comparable remedial interventions. (i.e. Angrist et al., 2025; Banerjee et al., 2016, 2023). Moreover, we find no evidence that the parental component generates additional gains beyond those achieved by the stand-alone literacy intervention.

We discuss two potential explanations for these findings. First, given randomization at the household rather than the school level, we cannot exclude within-school spillovers affecting the control group. Even though our ITT estimates plausibly provide a lower bound for treatment effects, substantial spillovers to the control group could attenuate estimated impacts. Second, we consider a set of intervention-related frictions that may have limited program effectiveness, including constraints on implementation intensity, sample heterogeneity, and barriers to parental engagement.

4.1 Spillovers

Ideally, randomization is implemented at the highest level at which spillovers are expected in order to avoid contamination of the control group (Miguel and Kremer, 2004). In our study, the decision to randomize at the household level rather than at the school level was primarily driven by budget constraints. While this design choice raises concerns about potential spillovers, the existing experimental evidence on remedial education programs that explicitly examines effects on non-targeted, higher-

Table 3: ITT estimates: Subconcepts

	Literacy	Literacy+ parents	Control mean %	N
Writing				
Writing	0.167*** (0.060)	0.161*** (0.060)	0.493	580
Motor skills	-0.164* (0.098)	-0.147 (0.099)	0.734	580
Reading				
Reading	0.037 (0.064)	0.063 (0.061)	0.723	580
Reading comprehension	0.122** (0.058)	0.058 (0.058)	0.392	580
Reading fluency	0.096 (0.064)	-0.090 (0.062)	0.361	580
Listening				
Listening comprehension	-0.099 (0.108)	0.037 (0.100)	0.833	580
Metalinguistic skills				
Phonological awareness	0.001 (0.072)	-0.005 (0.075)	0.418	580
Orthography	0.089 (0.097)	-0.000 (0.096)	0.155	580
Grammar	-0.095 (0.076)	-0.054 (0.081)	0.378	580

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline with complete baseline data is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

performing students provides little indication of meaningful spillovers, particularly relative to the magnitude of direct treatment effects (Banerjee et al., 2007; Saavedra

et al., 2019; Berlinski et al., 2023). To the extent that any spillovers are present, they would imply that our estimated treatment effects constitute a lower bound on the total impact of the intervention, with spillover effects expected to be small in comparison to the direct effects on treated students.

Nonetheless, we see four plausible channels through which the intervention could generate positive spillovers onto untreated students. First, the pull-out of treated students for remedial instruction mechanically reduces class size, potentially benefiting remaining students through a lower student–teacher ratio, allowing teachers to support the remaining low-performing students more effectively (e.g., Duflo et al., 2015; Urquiola and Verhoogen, 2009). Second, improvements among treated students may directly affect untreated peers through academic interactions (e.g., Berlinski et al., 2023). Third, the temporary removal of lower-performing students changes classroom peer composition, potentially increasing the exposure of other low-performing, but untreated students to higher-performing peers and reducing classroom disruption and improving the learning environment for remaining students. Fourth, teachers and peers may have indirectly adopted elements of the remedial approach.

Although the experiment does not allow us to isolate spillover effects on control students using purely experimental variation, the design induces between-classroom variation in exposure to treated peers. This variation stems from the fact that treatment was randomized within schools and baseline achievement strata, but not within grades or classrooms. To characterize peer exposure, we proxy classroom size using Ministry of Education end-of-year administrative data from the year preceding the intervention, which provide total grade-level enrollment by school for students in grades 1 through 9 (our sample does not observe total class size). Nearly all schools in the sample operate a single classroom per grade; only seven of the 126 targeted classrooms are located in school–grade cells with multiple sections.⁹ We then construct a leave-one-out measure of peer treatment intensity, defined as the fraction of classmates assigned to treatment, excluding the student herself if treated. The average classroom size is 19 students, implying an average of 18 peers per student. As shown in Figure 4, peer treatment intensity exhibits considerable dispersion across students, spanning the full range from 0 to 66.6 percent.¹⁰

We exploit this variation to estimate learning spillovers on both treated and control

⁹We proxy 2025 enrollment using 2024 enrollment in the grade below. For the seven school–grade cells with two classrooms, we divide grade-level enrollment evenly across sections.

¹⁰The upper bound reflects classrooms in which all students were part of the sample, consistent with an experimental design in which roughly one third of students were assigned to the control group.

Figure 4: Distribution of the Share of Treated Classmates

Notes: Self is excluded from both the treatment count and class size.

students. If spillovers are present, student achievement should be higher in classrooms with a larger share of students assigned to remedial literacy sessions. We test this hypothesis adapting Equation 1 the following way:

$$Y_{ihc} = \alpha + \gamma T_h + \sum_{k=2}^4 \delta_k \mathbb{1}\{E_c^{-h} \in \mathcal{B}_k\} + \sum_{k=2}^4 \rho_k T_h \times \mathbb{1}\{E_c^{-h} \in \mathcal{B}_k\} + \beta X_{ih} + \lambda S_h + \varepsilon_{ihc} \quad (2)$$

where Y_{ihc} denotes the endline outcome of student i in household h and classroom c , and T_h indicates household-level treatment assignment. Classroom-level treatment exposure is captured by a set of indicator variables $\mathbb{1}\{E_c^{-h} \in \mathcal{B}_k\}$ for k exposure bins. Our main specification uses $k = 4$ bins; we additionally report robustness checks for $k \in \{3, \dots, 6\}$ in the Appendix. As shown in Figure 4, the upper tail of the exposure distribution is thin; accordingly, the highest bin pools the top 10 percent of the distribution, spanning exposure values from 43% to 67%, in order to preserve statistical power. The remaining bins are equally spaced across the bottom 90% of the distribution. Standard errors are clustered at the classroom level, the level at which exposure varies. To increase statistical power and simplify interpretation, we pool the two treatment arms, as the spillover mechanisms discussed above are expected to operate similarly across treatments; results by treatment arm are reported in the Appendix. The coefficients δ_k capture spillover effects on control households

Figure 5: Spillovers to Control

Notes: Point estimates of δ_k from equation 2, capturing spillovers to control students. Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

across exposure bins, while γ measures the treatment–control difference in the lowest exposure bin and ρ_k allow peer effects to differ for treated households.

Figure 5 reports estimates of δ_k from equation 2, capturing spillover effects on control students across exposure bins. The figure presents results for three available standardized outcome measures proxying literacy skills: percent correct scores, IRT scores, and language grades. δ_k for $k = 1$ is zero by design, since control students at the lowest level of exposure represent the reference group. Consistent with positive spillovers, estimates of δ_k for all exposure bins are positive relative to the low-exposure reference group across all three outcomes, with almost all estimates statistically distinguishable from zero or close to conventional significance thresholds.

Across outcomes, spillover effects to control students generally increase with peer treatment exposure up to intermediate levels, consistent with a monotonic exposure–response relationship. The data provide support for this pattern over the range from 0 to 43% in peer exposure, while the distribution offers limited leverage to characterize the functional form beyond that point (see Figure 4). For example, moving from the lowest exposure bin to the 14.5% – 29% and 29% – 43.5% bins is associated with gains of roughly 0.1–0.14 and 0.33–0.38 standard deviations for control students, depending on the outcome. Estimates in the highest exposure bin are also positive across outcomes, but exhibit less consistent patterns and larger confidence intervals. This bin aggregates the upper tail of the exposure distribution (43% – 67%) and contains only about 10 percent of observations, so estimates at this level should be interpreted with more caution.

These magnitudes are economically meaningful. In our sample, the average student is exposed to 22.7 percent treated peers within her class, which lies close to the center of the second exposure bin (14.5% - 29%). Spillovers for that student can therefore be approximated by the estimates in this range, implying gains of approximately 0.1–0.14 standard deviations for average control students. These magnitudes are consistent with spillover effects from a remedial intervention for low-performing students in Colombia reported by Berlinski et al. (2023). They randomize treatment at the school level and find spillover gains of about 0.11 standard deviations among untreated, high-performing students, comparing treated and control schools, in a context where roughly one quarter (25.8%) of students are eligible for remedial instruction. Although identification strategy and the population experiencing spillovers differs, the resulting magnitudes given average exposure are very comparable.

Despite randomized treatment assignment and conditioning on baseline achievement, sex, age, and strata fixed effects, class-level treatment exposure need not be exogenous. Two considerations underlie this concern. First, treatment intensity is mechanically correlated with class size, as class size enters its denominator. If class size is systematically related to achievement—for instance through student–teacher ratios (e.g., Duflo et al., 2015; Urquiola and Verhoogen, 2009)—this mechanical relationship could bias estimates of δ_k upward. Second, lower treatment intensity mechanically implies higher average baseline literacy at the class level. Exposure to higher-performing peers may affect the outcomes of low-performing students in either direction, due to peer learning or possible reallocation of instruction toward higher-achieving students.

Figure A3 and A4 thus report robustness specifications that address these concerns. Contrary to concerns of upward bias, point estimates of δ_k increase slightly across outcomes when controlling for class size (see Figure A3), though differences are small and statistical significance remains broadly unchanged, with only a modest loss in precision. We also use administrative data from the Ministry of Education on standardized test scores (“Conociendo mis logros”) at the school–grade level in 2024. Although these data exhibit substantial missingness (44%), they permit proxying class-level achievement, again by using test scores from the preceding grade. Missing observations are set to zero, with a missingness indicator included in the regression. Figure A4 presents the resulting estimates, which remain largely stable in magnitude but are somewhat noisier.¹¹

The estimated spillover effects on control students are consistent with evidence

¹¹Alternatively, and to avoid missingness, we can also control for the number of sample (low-performing) students as a measure of average classroom performance; the conclusions are unchanged.

from qualitative interviews (see Figure A6). Four of the six interviewed teachers, representing different grades and schools, report some form of spillovers to control students, including reduced class sizes; peer interactions in which higher-performing students support lower-performing peers or treated peers share what they learned during the intervention; and teachers’ adoption of intervention exercises and instructional strategies.

Figure A2 presents estimates across peer-exposure bins for the pooled treated group, expressed relative to the low-exposure control group. Each estimate corresponds to the linear combination $\gamma + \rho_k + \delta_k$ in equation 2, capturing both direct treatment effects compared to low-exposure control students and spillovers to treated students. Consistent with the presence of spillovers to the control group, comparisons between treated and control students in the lowest peer-exposure bin (0–14.5%) reveal a positive direct treatment effect of approximately 0.16–0.21 standard deviations. This effect is statistically significant for percent-correct scores ($p = 0.08$), IRT scores ($p = 0.04$), and language school grades ($p = 0.10$). Point estimates for treated students provide limited evidence of relevant additional spillovers among treated students: although they exhibit a slight increase with peer treatment exposure, the pattern is not robust across outcome measures. As above, we approximate treatment effects at average exposure using the second bin (14.5% – 29%), yielding effects of 0.20–0.25 standard deviations for the average treated student. As with control spillover results, both point estimates and standard errors remain largely unchanged when controlling for class size or average class-level literacy scores (Figures A3 and A4). Figure A2 additionally reports unpooled estimates by treatment arm; the interpretation remains unchanged.

4.2 Intervention-Related Frictions

Section 4.1 documents non-negligible spillovers to control students, while Figures 6 and A2 suggest that direct treatment effects in the range of 0.20–0.25 standard deviations are likely. Although economically meaningful, these estimates remain smaller than impacts reported for the most successful remedial programs (see, e.g., Angrist et al., 2025; Banerjee et al., 2016), that have led the Global Education Evidence Advisory Panel (GEEAP) to characterize targeted remedial instruction as a “best buy” in education (Banerjee et al., 2023).

We therefore examine a set of intervention-related frictions that may have attenuated impacts for both treatments in our setting, including constraints on treatment

Figure 6: Spillovers to Treatment

Notes: Point estimates of the linear combination $\gamma + \rho_k + \delta_k$ from equation 2, capturing spillovers to treated students. Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

intensity, heterogeneity across students, and barriers to sustained parental engagement.

4.2.1 Treatment Intensity

Limited treatment intensity may have diluted the estimated impacts. The implementing NGO initially planned to deliver 40 sessions of 90 minutes over a 20-week period, an intensity comparable to that of other successful remedial interventions (e.g., Banerjee et al., 2016, who provide 40 days of 1.5-hour remedial language instruction in Uttar Pradesh). However, a two-month delay in approval by the Ministry of Education substantially shortened the effective implementation window (see the timeline in Figure 2). As a result, only 30–35 sessions could be delivered before the end of the school year. In addition, school-specific activities—some mandated by the Ministry—occasionally displaced scheduled sessions. Given the compressed timeline, it was not feasible to fully reschedule all missed sessions, generating minor variation in the total number of sessions delivered across schools.¹²

Beyond constraints on treatment offer, treatment uptake was also limited. Table 4 reports compliance statistics for students and parents. Although sessions were delivered during regular class hours and participation in at least some sessions was widespread (> 95% of students attended at least one session), students who attended

¹²This variation is negligible relative to the total number of sessions delivered in each school and plausibly exogenous.

consistently were not the majority: Only 47.3% and 53.0% of students in treatment arms 1 and 2 attended at least 75% of sessions, and just 23.2% and 24.7% were present for 90% or more of sessions.¹³ In line with these findings, treatment-on-the-treated estimates using a binary compliance indicator for participation in at least 75% of sessions, imply coefficients of 0.13 and 0.07 standard deviations for treatments 1 and 2, respectively, roughly doubling the corresponding intention-to-treat estimates (see Table A9).

Table 4: Program Participation by Treatment Group

	T1: Literacy	T2: Literacy + parents
Students		
≥ 1 session, %	95.5	98.2
≥ 50% of sessions, %	75.4	84.3
≥ 75% of sessions, %	47.3	53.4
≥ 90% of sessions, %	23.2	24.7
Parents		
≥ Session 1, %	-	76.7
≥ Session 2, %	-	44.4
≥ Session 3, %	-	20.6

This table reports program participation rates by treatment group. The number of sessions delivered varied between 30 and 35 due to unexpected disruptions such as school-specific activities. Thresholds of 50%, 75%, and 90% correspond to 16, 24, and 29 sessions attended for the median school. The parent component delivered 3 sessions, all of which were delivered in every school.

4.2.2 Sample Heterogeneity and Targeting

Despite the intention to target the intervention only to the lowest-performing students by asking teachers to identify struggling students using a simple decision rule¹⁴, substantial heterogeneity in ability remained: at baseline, two students answered none of the exam items correctly, while the highest score reached 88%.

This is important because a defining feature of many highly successful remedial programs, some of which report impacts of up to 0.7 standard deviations, is the grouping of students by ability level (Banerjee et al., 2016, 2007). This ensures each student

¹³For participation statistics over time see Figure A1

¹⁴Teachers classified students as struggling if they had difficulty reading a short paragraph aloud with comprehension and/or writing a simple sentence.

receives instruction aligned with their current skill level, rather than with the nominal grade curriculum. Such programs are commonly referred to in the literature as Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL). Although our program targeted low-performing students only, baseline assessments suggest that meaningful residual heterogeneity persisted, potentially limiting program effectiveness.

To assess this mechanism, we revisit evidence from one of the most influential experimental studies in remedial education. Banerjee et al. (2016) evaluate a sequence of randomized controlled trials in India that test alternative implementations of TaRL pedagogy, iteratively adapting program design to identify effective delivery models. Their most successful implementation in Uttar Pradesh uses a brief baseline assessment to group students in grades three to five across grade boundaries into ability-based groups. Instruction is then delivered at the appropriate level during intensive in-school learning camps totaling 40 days. This version generates learning gains of 0.61–0.7 standard deviations.

Banerjee et al. (2016) classify students into five learning levels—Beginner, Letter, Word, Paragraph, and Story—based on a brief diagnostic reading assessment. Students are categorized according to their ability to recognize letters, read words, read a short sentence or paragraph, or read a short story with relatively few errors (despite limited reading comprehension). Usually, Beginner and Letter students as well as Word and Paragraph students are grouped in practice. We map students in our sample to this classification using four baseline items: letter recognition and reading, word reading, and the number of words read from a short story within one minute. Students are assigned to the three lowest categories using a 50 percent correctness threshold for letter recognition/reading and word reading. To distinguish between the Word, Paragraph, and Story levels, we apply reading-speed cutoffs of fewer than 20 words per minute and more than 50 words per minute.¹⁵ This classification aligns most with the TaRL assessment framework developed by Pratham.

Figure 7 illustrates substantial differences in baseline heterogeneity when student ability is mapped to Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) categories. Despite the project being explicitly targeted toward low-performing students, the baseline ability distribution in our sample is markedly more heterogeneous than that observed

¹⁵Specifically, students are classified sequentially. A student who correctly recognizes or reads fewer than 50% of letters is classified as Beginner. Among remaining students, those who correctly read fewer than 50% of words are classified at the Letter level. Students who pass both thresholds but read fewer than 20 words per minute from the short story are classified at the Word level. Students who read between 20 and 50 words per minute are classified at the Paragraph level, while those reading more than 50 words per minute are classified at the Story level.

Figure 7: Distribution of baseline learning levels

Notes: Panel (a) shows the distribution of baseline learning levels in Uttar Pradesh from the original Teaching at the Right Level (TaRL) experiment (Banerjee et al., 2016). Panel (b) shows the distribution of baseline learning levels in our experiment, mapped to the classification criteria used in Banerjee et al. (2016).

in Uttar Pradesh, where TaRL was implemented among all students within treated schools. In Uttar Pradesh, 79% of students fall into the Beginner or Letter categories, which are typically grouped together, compared with only 41% in our sample. Conversely, more than one-third of students in our sample (34%) is classified at the Story level, indicating the ability to read short stories with relatively few errors, whereas the corresponding share in Uttar Pradesh is only 8%. Although our sample includes students from grades two and six, as well as a small number of secondary students, this is unlikely to account for the observed differences for two reasons. First, sampling criteria explicitly targeted the lowest-performing students. Second, the pronounced left-skewness of the distribution in Uttar Pradesh is unlikely to be substantially affected by modest reweighting at the extremes (second and sixth grade) of the grade distribution.

This heterogeneity may have constrained learning gains for two related reasons. First, Banerjee et al. (2016) find that the grouping is critical to success in their setting. Remedial instruction delivered without regrouping students by ability does not generate statistically significant improvements relative to the control group. Second, a careful examination of our instructional materials reveals a strong tilt toward lower to medium ability levels. After classifying materials according to TaRL categories, we find that 62% of exercises target the Beginner and Letter levels and 31% the Word and Paragraph levels, while only 7% are designed for the Story level. Since 34% of students in our sample fall into this highest category, the resulting mismatch between student ability and instructional content may have limited program effectiveness for

them. This pattern aligns with our heterogeneity analysis, indicating that the interventions were more effective for lower-performing students, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds and without a literate parent at home (see Table A10).

4.2.3 Parental Component

Intention-to-treat estimates from Section 3 reveal no differential impact of the additional parent component on literacy outcomes ($0.43 \leq p \leq 0.85$). Spillover analyses in Section 4.1 similarly show no systematic differences between the two treatment arms when each is compared to the lowest-exposure control group. Taken together, these results indicate that the added parent component did not generate measurable gains in literacy over literacy-only sessions.

Our theory of change requires a sequence of three conditions through which support offered to parents can translate into gains in student learning. Parents must first be exposed to the intervention by receiving the informational inputs. Conditional on exposure, they must possess both the capacity and the motivation to convert these inputs into active support for their children’s learning at home. Finally, even when implemented as intended, the prescribed activities may fail to generate improvements in learning. We present evidence on the links in this causal chain and identify the stage at which the intervention most likely lost effectiveness.

We begin by examining parental exposure to the intervention. Administrative data from WhatsApp group chats indicate high levels of message receipt: the median parent has zero unread messages (see top-left panel of Figure 8). We are unable to observe message-read rates in individual chats, as WhatsApp allows users to disable read receipts.

We next examine whether the intervention increased parental engagement, the second step in our theory of change. Table 5 presents intent to treat estimates for secondary outcomes, including measures of parental involvement reported by students. We find no evidence that parents in the second treatment arm provided greater motivational support or increased assistance with schoolwork ($p = 0.63$ and $p = 0.86$), also when accounting for potential spillovers (see Figure A6).

Three mechanisms could account for this null result. Parents may have lacked either the motivation and interest, the time or the capacity to engage. The available evidence favors one of the first two interpretations. Parental responsiveness to the intervention was low. Reactions to messages in group and individual chats such as emojis, acknowledgments, feedback, or questions were sparse: the median parent responded to only 10% of both individual and group messages (Figure 8). Active

Figure 8: Parental engagement with WhatsApp messages

Notes: Panel (a) shows parent engagement in WhatsApp group chats. Panel (b) shows parent engagement in individual WhatsApp chats. Group chats allow distinguishing between receipt and reading of messages; individual chats do not. “Reactions” include anything from emojis to brief acknowledgments or feedback and questions. The orange dashed line represents the median.

participation also declined sharply over time. Attendance at the three focus meetings was 76%, 44%, and 20% respectively (Table 4). This pattern is also consistent with evidence from semi-structured interviews with teachers (see Table A6), in which four of six respondents cite increased parental motivation and engagement as a potential avenue for improvement. It is possible that increased in-school support crowded out parental engagement; however, we cannot directly test this hypothesis, as we do not include a parent-only treatment arm.

By contrast, we find little support for capacity constraints. Literacy rates among parents are high: seventy four percent of students in the second treatment arm have two literate parents (Table 1). We also detect no treatment heterogeneity of the parental component by co-residency with at least one literate parent at baseline (Table A10).

Finally, we cannot rule out that the parental component could have improved learning outcomes if parents had consistently implemented the advice and exercises.

5 Conclusion

We implement a randomized controlled trial on remedial literacy in rural El Salvador that reflects a policy-real approach: pull-out, small-group instruction conducted dur-

Table 5: ITT estimates: Reported Parent Engagement

	Parents motivate	Parents help
Literacy	0.061 (0.046)	0.002 (0.050)
Literacy+ parents	0.023 (0.046)	-0.008 (0.050)
N	580	580

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline with complete baseline data is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

ing the school day by external facilitators, delivered schoolwide across grades, and targeted using teacher discretion. Our pre-specified intention-to-treat estimates are small and statistically imprecise for both treatments. Their magnitude is consistent with pre-specified power limits, but masks an important feature of the experimental environment: interference within schools.

Spillovers for the average low-performing but untreated student are estimated to amount to 0.10–0.14 standard deviations ($0.04 \leq p \leq 0.25$), whereas the average treated students experiences an increase of 0.20–0.25 standard deviations ($0.03 \leq p \leq 0.08$) in learning compared to low-exposure control students. These estimates are corroborated by semi-structured interviews with teachers.

Although the evidence suggests that direct treatment effects were meaningful, we present support for three channels that may have dampened impacts in both treatments: a shortened implementation period with moderate compliance, heterogeneity in baseline student literacy, and limited parental engagement.

The results also speak to external validity. While most experimental evidence on remedial education comes from India and Sub-Saharan Africa, we provide policy-real evidence from Latin America, showing that targeted remediation can generate meaningful learning gains.

Taken together, the findings highlight a potential trade-off: practical, low-cost targeting and real-world implementation constraints may attenuate average treatment effects, yet positive spillovers can partially offset the welfare costs arising from imperfect targeting and implementation frictions. For policymakers, this implies that program assessment should incorporate indirect effects, not only direct effects on the

treated, when judging whether remedial support is cost-effective and scalable. For researchers, the results motivate future work on (i) the optimal intensity of remedial instruction, (ii) the supports that help ensure student attendance and participation, and (iii) more intensive parent-facing designs that translate information into practice.

Bibliography

- Altinok, N., Angrist, N., and Patrinos, H. A. (2018). Global data set on education quality (1965-2015). *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (8314).
- Amaral, S., Dinarte-Diaz, L., Dominguez, P., and Perez-Vincent, S. M. (2024). Helping families help themselves: The (un-)intended impacts of a digital parenting program. *Journal of Development Economics*, 166:103181.
- Anderson, M. L. (2008). Multiple inference and gender differences in the effects of early intervention: A reevaluation of the abecedarian, Perry Preschool, and Early Training Projects. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 103(484):1481–1495. Publisher: Informa UK Limited.
- Angelucci, M. and De Giorgi, G. (2009). Indirect effects of an aid program: How do cash transfers affect ineligibles’ consumption? *American Economic Review*, 99(1):486–508.
- Angrist, N., Ainomugisha, M., Bathena, S. P., Bergman, P., Crossley, C., Cullen, C., Letsomo, T., Matsheng, M., Panti, R. M., Sabarwal, S., et al. (2023). Building resilient education systems: Evidence from large-scale randomized trials in five countries. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Angrist, N., Bergman, P., and Matsheng, M. (2022). Experimental evidence on learning using low-tech when school is out. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 6(7):941–950.
- Angrist, N., Djankov, S., Goldberg, P. K., and Patrinos, H. A. (2021). Measuring human capital using global learning data. *Nature*, 592(7854):403–408.
- Angrist, N., Evans, D. K., Filmer, D., Glennerster, R., Rogers, H., and Sabarwal, S. (2025). How to improve education outcomes most efficiently? A review of the evidence using a unified metric. *Journal of Development Economics*, 172:103382.
- Aurino, E. and Wolf, S. (2024). A ‘smart buy’ for all? Unequal and unintended consequences of a messaging program for child education. *UB Economics–Working Papers*, 2024 E24/461.
- Banerjee, A., Banerji, R., Andrabi, T., Dynarski, S., Glennerster, R., Grantham-McGregor, S., Muralidharan, K., Piper, B., Saavedra, J., Yoshikawa, H., Ruto, S., and Schmelkes, S. (2023). Cost-effective approaches to improve global learning - what does recent evidence tell us are “smart buys” for improving learning in low-

- and middle-income countries? Recommendations of the Global Education Evidence Advisory Panel (GEEAP), World Bank Group, London, Washington D.C., New York.
- Banerjee, A., Banerji, R., Berry, J., Duflo, E., Kannan, H., Mukherji, S., Shotland, M., and Walton, M. (2016). Mainstreaming an effective intervention: Evidence from randomized evaluations of “Teaching at the Right Level” in India. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Banerjee, A. V., Banerji, R., Duflo, E., Glennerster, R., and Khemani, S. (2010). Pitfalls of participatory programs: Evidence from a randomized evaluation in education in India. *American Economic Journal: Economic Policy*, 2(1):1–30.
- Banerjee, A. V., Cole, S., Duflo, E., and Linden, L. (2007). Remedying education: Evidence from two randomized experiments in India. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 122(3):1235–1264.
- Banerji, R., Berry, J., and Shotland, M. (2013). The impact of mother literacy and participation programs on child learning: Evidence from a randomized evaluation in India. *Cambridge, MA: Abdul Latif Jameel Poverty Action Lab (J-PAL)*, page 84.
- Berlinski, S., Busso, M., and Giannola, M. (2023). Helping struggling students and benefiting all: Peer effects in primary education. *Journal of Public Economics*, 224:104925.
- Bettinger, E., Cunha, N., Lichand, G., and Madeira, R. (2021). Are the effects of informational interventions driven by salience? *Working paper series/Department of Economics*, (350).
- Bobonis, G. J. and Finan, F. (2009). Neighborhood peer effects in secondary school enrollment decisions. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 91(4):695–716.
- Büchel, K., Jakob, M., Kühnhanss, C., Steffen, D., and Brunetti, A. (2022). The relative effectiveness of teachers and learning software: Evidence from a field experiment in El Salvador. *Journal of Labor Economics*, 40(3):737–777.
- Cabezas, V., Cuesta, J. I., and Gallego, F. A. (2021). *Does Short-term School Tutoring Have Medium-term Effects?: Experimental Evidence from Chile*. Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile.

- Chimbutane, F., Karachiwalla, N., Herrera-Almanza, C., Leight, J., and Lauchande, C. (2026). The effect of teacher training and community literacy programming on teacher and student outcomes. *Journal of Development Economics*, 178:103578.
- Coccia, C., Jakob, M., Buchel, K., and Jann, B. (2026). When better teachers aren't enough: An experimental evaluation of teacher training programs in El Salvador. forthcoming. Registered at the AEA RCT Registry, ID 0010035.
- Cortes, K. E., Fricke, H., Loeb, S., Song, D. S., and York, B. N. (2021). Too little or too much? Actionable advice in an early-childhood text messaging experiment. *Education Finance and Policy*, 16(2):209–232.
- Dixon, P., Schagen, I., and Seedhouse, P. (2011). The impact of an intervention on children's reading and spelling ability in low-income schools in India. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 22(4):461–482.
- Dizon-Ross, R. (2019). Parents' beliefs about their children's academic ability: Implications for educational investments. *American Economic Review*, 109(8):2728–2765.
- Duflo, A., Kiessel, J., and Lucas, A. (2020). Experimental evidence on alternative policies to increase learning at scale. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Duflo, E., Dupas, P., and Kremer, M. (2011). Peer effects, teacher incentives, and the impact of tracking: Evidence from a randomized evaluation in Kenya. *American Economic Review*, 101(5):1739–1774.
- Duflo, E., Dupas, P., and Kremer, M. (2015). School governance, teacher incentives, and pupil–teacher ratios: Experimental evidence from Kenyan primary schools. *Journal of Public Economics*, 123:92–110.
- Hanushek, E. A. (2013). Economic growth in developing countries: The role of human capital. *Economics of Education Review*, 37:204–212.
- Hanushek, E. A. and Woessmann, L. (2012a). Do better schools lead to more growth? Cognitive skills, economic outcomes, and causation. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 17:267–321.
- Hanushek, E. A. and Woessmann, L. (2012b). Schooling, educational achievement, and the Latin American growth puzzle. *Journal of Development Economics*, 99(2):497–512.

- Hernández-Agramonte, J. M., Namen, O., Näslund-Hadley, E., and Biehl, M. L. (2022). Improving early childhood development outcomes in times of COVID-19: Experimental evidence on parental networks and SMS messages. Technical report, IDB Working Paper Series.
- Kigobe, J., Van den Noortgate, W., Ligembe, N., Ogondiek, M., Ghesquière, P., and Van Leeuwen, K. (2021). Effects of a parental involvement intervention to promote child literacy in Tanzania: A cluster randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness*, 14(4):770–791.
- Kim, Y.-S. G., Lee, H., and Zuilkowski, S. S. (2020). Impact of literacy interventions on reading skills in low-and middle-income countries: A meta-analysis. *Child Development*, 91(2):638–660.
- Marinelli, H. A., Berlinski, S., and Busso, M. (2024). Remedial education: Evidence from a sequence of experiments in Colombia. *Journal of Human Resources*, 59(1):141–174.
- Mateo Díaz, M., Becerra Luna, L., Hernández-Agramonte, J. M., López Bóo, F., Pérez Alfaro, M., and Vasquez Echeverria, A. (2020). Nudging parents to increase preschool attendance in Uruguay. Technical report, IDB Working Paper Series.
- Mendelsohn, A. L., da Rosa Piccolo, L., Oliveira, J. B. A., Mazzuchelli, D. S., Lopez, A. S., Cates, C. B., and Weisleder, A. (2020). Rct of a reading aloud intervention in brazil: Do impacts differ depending on parent literacy? *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 53:601–611.
- Miguel, E. and Kremer, M. (2004). Worms: identifying impacts on education and health in the presence of treatment externalities. *Econometrica*, 72(1):159–217.
- Ome, A. and Menendez, A. (2022). Using SMS and parental outreach to improve early reading skills in Zambia. *Education Economics*, 30(4):384–398.
- Patel, D. and Sandefur, J. (2020). A Rosetta Stone for human capital. Working Paper 550, Center for Global Development.
- Pouzevara, S. and King, S. (2014). MobiLiteracy-Uganda program phase 1: Endline report. *RTI International*.
- Pritchett, L. and Beatty, A. (2015). Slow down, you’re going too fast: Matching curricula to student skill levels. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 40:276–288.

- Saavedra, J., Näslund-Hadley, E., and Alfonso, M. (2017). Targeted remedial education: Experimental evidence from Peru. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Saavedra, J. E., Näslund-Hadley, E., and Alfonso, M. (2019). Remedial inquiry-based science education: Experimental evidence from Peru. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 41(4):483–509.
- Secretaría de Educación Pública de México (2010). Estándares nacionales de habilidad lectora. Available at . Last accessed: 2025-12-13.
- Stone, R., de Hoop, T., Coombes, A., and Nakamura, P. (2019). What works to improve early grade literacy in Latin America and the Caribbean? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 16(1):e1067.
- Urquiola, M. and Verhoogen, E. (2009). Class-size caps, sorting, and the regression-discontinuity design. *American Economic Review*, 99(1):179–215.

A Appendix

A1 Assessment Data

A1.1 Primary Outcome

The primary outcome variable of the study is the students' aggregated endline score, which is an index of the subtasks included in the test.

a) Motor skills

- **Tracing lines (Q2a-c → contains subtasks):** Students should trace different patterns. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly or partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.¹⁶

b) Writing

- **Writing of own name (Q1):** Students should write down their own name. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Writing of letters (Q3a-f → contains subtasks):** Students should copy letters. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Writing of words (Q4a-c → contains subtasks):** Students should copy words. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Writing of names of pictures (Q7a-c → contains subtasks):** Students should write down the names of printed pictures. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Writing sentences that describe pictures (10a-b → contains subtasks):** Students should write down single sentences to describe printed pictures. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Writing a history (Q21):** Students should write down some sentences that they should invent themselves. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved

¹⁶At baseline, there were almost no students who solved these subtasks fully correctly, which is why partially correctly is also coded as 1.

incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

c) **Reading**

- **Connection of words and pictures (Q5):** Students should connect pictures and the corresponding words. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Connection of sentences and pictures (Q6):** Students should connect pictures and the corresponding sentences. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Connection of words and sentences (Q8):** Students should connect words and the corresponding sentences. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Connection of a sentence and an image (Q9):** From three images students should choose the one that corresponds to a sentence. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Identification of single letters (Q22a-z → contains subtasks):** Students should identify all the letters. These were being read to them in random order. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Reading letters aloud (Q23a-f → contains subtasks):** Students should read aloud six letters that were shown to them. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Reading words aloud (Q24a-o → contains subtasks):** Students should read aloud 15 words. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

d) **Reading comprehension**

- **Answering reading comprehension questions (Q16a-d → contains subtasks):** Students should read a brief text and answer comprehension questions. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Answer a reading comprehension question in the oral part (Q25d):** After having read a short text, students should answer a comprehension

question. The subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

e) **Reading fluency**

- **Words correct per minute (25a-b):** Students should read a text within one minute. The number of words read, minus the number of words read incorrectly, is recorded. It is then categorized using two thresholds: students who read fewer than 40 words are assigned 0, those who read between 40 and 79 words are assigned 0.5, and those who read 80 words or more are assigned 1. This is informed by reading fluency benchmarks in Spanish set by the Mexican Ministry of Education, indicating that third-grade students should be able to read 80 words per minute.¹⁷ (Secretaría de Educación Pública de México, 2010)
- **Reading of a brief text (Q25c):** Facilitators note how the student reads. The task is coded as 0 if the student does not read, as 0.5 if it reads with errors and as 1 if it reads without errors.

f) **Phonological awareness**

- **Recognize vowels (Q17):** Students should identify the vowels from a mixture of vowels and consonants. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Recognize capital letters (Q18):** Students should identify capital letters from a mixture of capital and lowercase letters. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Recognize punctuation marks (Q19):** Students should identify punctuation marks from a mixture of punctuation marks and letters. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Allocate correct articles (Q20):** Students should allocate the corresponding articles to words represented as images. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Separate words into syllables (Q15):** Students should separate words into syllables. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

¹⁷We use third-grade competency as a benchmark since we expect children to have developed reading competency by this point.

g) **Listening comprehension**

- **Answering listening comprehension questions (Q26a-c → contains subtasks):** Students are read a text and should answer comprehension questions. Each subtask is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly, as 0.5 if it is solved partially correctly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

h) **Orthography**

- **Capitalization (Q12):** From four sentences, students should choose the one that is written correctly (taking into account upper and lower case letters). The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Spelling (Q14):** Students are shown four incomplete words and must select the one that is correctly completed with the given letter (e.g., “b”). The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

i) **Grammar**

- **Words in context (Q11):** From four verbs, students should choose the one that correctly completes a sentence. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.
- **Tenses (Q13):** From four conjugated verbs, students should choose the one that is in the past tense. The task is coded as 0 if it is solved incorrectly and as 1 if it is solved correctly.

Endline score - weighted:

The main measure of students’ endline literacy is a weighted score of all the questions listed above. If questions consist of subtasks, the mean of the subtasks is calculated. The subtasks of questions 16 (answering reading comprehension questions), 25 (words correct per minute), and 26 (answering listening comprehension questions) are counted separately, because the effort and importance of the subtasks is similar to other main tasks. Questions 22 and 24 enter the index with double weight, because they are relatively long but include several subtasks that, individually, would not warrant full weighting. Finally, these values (ranging from 0 to 1) are averaged to produce a score for each student, also scaled between 0 and 1.

A1.2 Secondary Outcomes

In addition to literacy skills, we also evaluate non-cognitive outcomes that may be affected by the interventions. These outcomes capture students' attitudes, motivation and socio-emotional skills.

- **Socio-emotional skills:** Students are asked a series of statements and indicate the extent to which they agree with each one using a four-point Likert scale (“*Never*,” “*Rarely*,” “*Often*,” and “*Always*”). Responses are recoded such that 1 corresponds to “*Never*”, 2 to “*Rarely*”, 3 to “*Often*” and 4 to “*Always*”. We group statements into three standardized indexes: attitude towards school, academic self-concept and perseverance and growth mindset. We also look at the individual statements in order to understand the meaning of indexes. Indexes are constructed using the approach described in Anderson (2008).¹⁸ Following Anderson (2008), missing values are (conservatively) replaced with the control group mean when building standardized indexes; for analyses of individual components, no imputation is applied.

- **Attitude towards school:**

- * I like going to school.
- * I feel happy at school.
- * I am motivated to learn things at school.

- **Academic self-concept:**

- * I am good at what we do at school.
- * I understand what they teach us at school.
- * I feel capable of doing difficult tasks.

- **Perseverance and growth mindset:**

- * I finish what I start.
- * When things don't work out the first time, I usually keep trying.
- * When I try hard, I get better in class.
- * I'm afraid of making mistakes in class (reverse coded).

- **Number of friends:** Number of friends the student names.

¹⁸If an index includes another standardized index, we compute the composite directly from the underlying variables.

- **School-related activities at home:** Students are asked how they spend their free time after school or on weekends, and their first three activities are recorded. We construct two measures: an indicator equal to 1 if the student’s top activity is school-related, and the share of school-related activities among the top three.
- **Future aspirations:**
 - **Plans to attend high school:** An indicator that equals 1 if the student thinks he/she will go to high school and 0 otherwise.
 - **Plans to attend university:** An indicator that equals 1 if the student thinks he/she will attend university and 0 otherwise.
 - **Aspires to educated profession:** An indicator that equals 1 if the student reports aspiring to a profession that requires a tertiary degree.

A2 Sample, Attrition and Compliance

Table A1: Comparison Schools in and out of the Sample

	Other schools in country (1)	Other schools in Morazán (2)	In the experiment (3)	Difference (3) - (2) (4)
Rural school (%)	74.62 (43.52) [4830]	84.26 (36.48) [305]	88.46 (32.58) [26]	4.20 (7.39)
Students, grades 2–6	172.88 (207.09) [4320]	91.27 (114.98) [273]	163.38 (75.35) [26]	72.11*** (23.03)
Teachers, grades 2–6	9.35 (7.38) [4300]	6.81 (4.48) [273]	8.81 (4.45) [26]	2.00** (0.92)
Schools with morning shift (%)	97.54 (15.50) [4830]	97.70 (15.00) [305]	100.00 (0.00) [26]	2.30 (2.95)
Schools with afternoon shift (%)	58.22 (49.32) [4830]	41.97 (49.43) [305]	76.92 (42.97) [26]	34.96*** (10.00)
Schools offering secondary grades (%)	32.38 (6.84) [2479]	34.86 (7.96) [118]	31.27 (4.65) [22]	-3.59** (1.75)
Conociendo Mis Logros test score (standardized)	51.84 (13.76) [4145]	55.65 (13.80) [281]	50.44 (10.18) [26]	-5.21* (2.78)

Column (1) reports means for schools outside the Department of Morazán. Column (2) reports means for schools in Morazán that are not part of the study sample, and Column (3) reports means for schools included in the experiment. Standard deviations are reported in parentheses and the number of observations in square brackets. Column (4) reports differences between non-sample schools in Morazán and schools in the experimental sample, along with standard errors of the differences (in parentheses). Data are from Ministry of Education administrative records. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A2: Attrition by Treatment Group

Attrition control group	T1: literacy	T2: literacy + parents	P-value
14.81%	-3.09 p.p. (3.29)	-3.66 p.p. (3.29)	0.508

This table reports attrition by treatment group. Column 1 is attrition in the control group. Columns 2 and 3 reports the difference in attrition compared to the control group estimated using OLS controlling for age, sex, baseline score, and strata fixed effects (standard errors in parentheses) Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The P-value corresponds to the joined hypothesis test (F-test) that T1=0 and T2=0. Observations: 663.

Figure A1: Student Participation Over Time

Table A3: Balance at Endline

	Control	T1: literacy	T2: literacy + parents	P-value
Age	10.011 (1.737)	9.990 (1.816)	9.919 (1.669)	0.524
Female	0.353 (0.479)	0.374 (0.485)	0.328 (0.471)	0.672
Baseline score	0.471 (0.228)	0.479 (0.226)	0.468 (0.228)	0.150
Socioeconomic background (PCA)	-0.003 (1.388)	0.022 (1.416)	-0.022 (1.441)	0.802
Household size	5.016 (1.703)	5.340 (2.222)	5.275 (1.980)	0.347
Lives with mother and father	0.581 (0.485)	0.488 (0.490)	0.581 (0.479)	0.119
Mother and father literate	0.712 (0.432)	0.745 (0.409)	0.752 (0.410)	0.727
Likes to go to school	0.940 (0.238)	0.954 (0.209)	0.932 (0.248)	0.595
Orthogonality Tests				
Joint orthogonality test				0.681
Bivariate: Control vs T1				0.236
Bivariate: Control vs T2				0.852
Bivariate: T1 vs T2				0.496

For non-attriters, columns 1-3 show the means of baseline characteristics for the different treatment groups (standard deviations in parentheses). Column 4 reports the p-values for the null hypothesis that treatment status does not predict individual variables, controlling for age, sex, baseline score and stratum fixed effects, except for age (does not include age fixed effects), sex (does not include sex fixed effects) and baseline score (does not include baseline score effects). The joint orthogonality test reports the p-value for the null hypothesis that all baseline variables are jointly uncorrelated with the treatment assignment. The bivariate tests report the p-value for the null hypothesis that the different pairings of treatment groups do not differ on any baseline variable. Orthogonality tests include age, sex, socioeconomic background index (PCA), baseline score, household size, an indicator of whether the child lives with its mother and one of whether it lives with its father, an indicator of whether it likes to go to school, and stratum fixed effects. Missing values of the baseline variables are imputed using the group mean. All standard errors are clustered at the household level. Observations per group: T1: 198, T2: 198, Control: 184.

Table A4: Attrition Balance

	Non-attritors	Attritors	P-value
Age	9.972 (1.739)	10.639 (2.156)	0.002
Female	0.352 (0.478)	0.325 (0.471)	0.754
Baseline score	0.473 (0.227)	0.390 (0.221)	0.172
Socioeconomic background (PCA)	-0.001 (1.414)	0.005 (1.736)	0.668
Household size	5.215 (1.987)	5.516 (2.301)	0.199
Lives with mother and father	0.549 (0.486)	0.555 (0.494)	0.897
Mother and father literate	0.737 (0.417)	0.627 (0.430)	0.507
Likes to go to school	0.942 (0.232)	0.914 (0.279)	0.512
Orthogonality Tests			
Joint orthogonality test			0.072
Bivariate: Attritors vs. Non-attritors			0.079

This table reports mean baseline characteristics for non-attritors and attritors (standard deviations in parentheses). The p-value reports the significance of the difference in means between attritors and non-attritors, estimated using OLS controlling for age, sex, baseline score, and strata fixed effects, except for age (no age controls), sex (no sex controls), and baseline score (no baseline score controls). Standard errors are clustered at the household level. Observations: Non-attritors = 580, Attritors = 83.

A3 Results

Table A5: ITT estimates: Main Outcomes without Controls

	Endline score	Endline score IRT
Literacy	0.126* (0.069)	0.116 (0.073)
Literacy+ parents	0.076 (0.064)	0.059 (0.068)
Control mean %	0.531	-0.028
N	580	580

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline is 584. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A6: ITT estimates: School Grades

	Math	Language	Science	Civics Values
Literacy	-0.004 (0.071)	0.073 (0.077)	0.068 (0.077)	0.054 (0.067)
Literacy+ parents	-0.009 (0.072)	0.060 (0.071)	0.044 (0.076)	0.068 (0.072)
N	620	620	619	594

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline with complete baseline data is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A7: ITT estimates: School Grades without Controls

	Math	Language	Science	Civics Values
Literacy	-0.034 (0.089)	0.082 (0.092)	0.056 (0.091)	0.034 (0.085)
Literacy+ parents	-0.012 (0.089)	0.038 (0.085)	0.047 (0.087)	0.015 (0.086)
Control mean %	6.256	6.314	6.374	6.636
N	621	621	620	595

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline is 584. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A8: ITT estimates: Secondary Outcomes

	Literacy	Literacy+ parents	Control mean %	N
Socio-emotional Outcomes				
School attitudes	-0.041 (0.099)	-0.063 (0.100)	0.000	580
Academic self-concept	0.040 (0.106)	0.032 (0.097)	-0.000	580
Perseverance	0.076 (0.108)	0.009 (0.104)	0.000	580
Friends				
Number of Friends	-0.479 (0.328)	-0.823*** (0.317)	5.228	580
Leisure Activities				
School-related activities	0.099 (0.109)	0.096 (0.107)	0.000	577
Future Aspirations				
Aspirations	-0.089 (0.092)	-0.152* (0.090)	0.000	580

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline with complete baseline data is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A9: TOT estimates: Main Outcomes with Controls

	T1	T2	T1 vs. T2
Binary instrument			
Endline score	0.127 (0.091)	0.076 (0.081)	-0.03 (0.121)
Endline score IRT	0.103 (0.094)	0.068 (0.086)	-0.096 (0.125)
Continuous instrument			
Endline score	0.096 (0.069)	0.06 (0.064)	-0.017 (0.07)
Endline score IRT	0.077 (0.07)	0.054 (0.068)	-0.056 (0.072)
N	382	374	388

T1 refers to the comparison between the treatment 1 (Literacy) and the control group; T2 refers to the comparison between the treatment 2 (Literacy + parents) and the control group; T1 vs. T2 refers to the comparison between the two treatment groups. All regressions include sex, age, baseline test score and strata fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. $*p < 0.1$; $**p < 0.05$; $***p < 0.01$

Table A10: Heterogeneity estimates: Main Outcomes - Main Specification

	Endline score	Endline score IRT
Female		
Lecto	0.048 (0.054)	0.022 (0.056)
Lecto+parents	0.095* (0.057)	0.052 (0.059)
Lecto* Female	0.073 (0.107)	0.137 (0.111)
(Lecto+parents)* Female	-0.134 (0.099)	-0.069 (0.105)
Median age		
Lecto	0.024 (0.067)	-0.033 (0.075)
Lecto+parents	0.036 (0.071)	-0.002 (0.075)
Lecto* Older	0.090 (0.100)	0.187* (0.106)
(Lecto+parents)* Older	0.022 (0.099)	0.051 (0.103)
Median score		
Lecto	0.112 (0.075)	0.084 (0.076)
Lecto+parents	0.131* (0.072)	0.073 (0.071)
Lecto* Above median	-0.084 (0.094)	-0.030 (0.098)
(Lecto+parents)* Above median	-0.164* (0.095)	-0.088 (0.099)
Median SES		
Lecto	0.165** (0.071)	0.145* (0.076)
Lecto+parents	0.118* (0.069)	0.085 (0.077)
Lecto* Above median	-0.158 (0.098)	-0.129 (0.103)
(Lecto+parents)* Above median	-0.120 (0.097)	-0.096 (0.103)
Lives with literate parent		
Lecto	0.242* (0.142)	0.306** (0.130)
Lecto+parents	0.087 (0.120)	0.084 (0.124)
Lecto* Lives with literate parent	-0.197 (0.150)	-0.274** (0.138)
(Lecto+parents)* Lives with literate parent	-0.044 (0.133)	-0.065 (0.137)

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. In case of baseline imbalances across heterogeneity subgroups, we also control for the respective imbalanced baseline variable. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Table A11: Heterogeneity estimates: Subconcepts - Main Specification

	Motor skills	Writing	Reading	Reading comprehension	Reading fluency	Phonological awareness	Listening comprehension	Ortography	Grammar
Female									
Lecto	-0.24*	0.18***	-0.01	0.10	0.11	0.02	0.02	0.02	-0.13
	(0.12)	(0.07)	(0.08)	(0.07)	(0.08)	(0.09)	(0.14)	(0.12)	(0.09)
Lecto+parents	-0.19	0.27***	0.08	0.07	0.00	0.04	0.09	-0.08	-0.03
	(0.13)	(0.07)	(0.08)	(0.07)	(0.08)	(0.09)	(0.13)	(0.12)	(0.10)
Lecto* Female	0.20	-0.04	0.18	0.11	0.01	-0.03	-0.32	0.22	0.13
	(0.21)	(0.13)	(0.13)	(0.13)	(0.14)	(0.17)	(0.23)	(0.23)	(0.17)
(Lecto+parents)* Female	0.10	-0.38***	-0.03	-0.05	-0.28**	-0.15	-0.12	0.23	-0.10
	(0.22)	(0.12)	(0.13)	(0.13)	(0.13)	(0.17)	(0.22)	(0.20)	(0.17)
Median age									
Lecto	-0.33**	0.13	-0.04	0.06	0.07	0.05	-0.04	0.13	-0.06
	(0.17)	(0.09)	(0.11)	(0.08)	(0.09)	(0.11)	(0.17)	(0.14)	(0.11)
Lecto+parents	-0.18	0.13	0.08	0.03	-0.18**	0.00	0.11	-0.11	-0.05
	(0.17)	(0.09)	(0.11)	(0.08)	(0.09)	(0.12)	(0.16)	(0.14)	(0.12)
Lecto* Older	0.29	0.08	0.17	0.14	0.08	-0.06	-0.11	-0.06	-0.04
	(0.22)	(0.12)	(0.14)	(0.12)	(0.13)	(0.16)	(0.22)	(0.21)	(0.16)
(Lecto+parents)* Older	0.04	0.03	-0.00	0.04	0.15	-0.02	-0.09	0.19	-0.03
	(0.22)	(0.12)	(0.13)	(0.12)	(0.13)	(0.16)	(0.21)	(0.20)	(0.16)
Median score									
Lecto	-0.20	0.24**	0.02	0.17**	0.13	0.09	-0.06	0.11	0.01
	(0.17)	(0.10)	(0.11)	(0.07)	(0.08)	(0.10)	(0.19)	(0.12)	(0.10)
Lecto+parents	0.00	0.31***	0.06	0.13*	0.01	0.11	0.01	-0.06	0.03
	(0.16)	(0.09)	(0.11)	(0.07)	(0.07)	(0.10)	(0.17)	(0.12)	(0.11)

Table A11: Heterogeneity estimates: Subconcepts - Main Specification (*continued*)

	Motor skills	Writing	Reading	Reading comprehension	Reading fluency	Phonological awareness	Listening comprehension	Ortography	Grammar
Lecto* Above median	0.03 (0.20)	-0.14 (0.12)	0.07 (0.13)	-0.09 (0.11)	-0.05 (0.13)	-0.15 (0.14)	-0.08 (0.22)	-0.02 (0.19)	-0.18 (0.15)
(Lecto+parents)* Above median	-0.31 (0.21)	-0.33*** (0.12)	0.02 (0.13)	-0.16 (0.12)	-0.21* (0.12)	-0.22 (0.15)	0.08 (0.20)	0.11 (0.20)	-0.18 (0.16)
Median SES									
Lecto	-0.26 (0.16)	0.29*** (0.09)	0.19** (0.09)	0.23** (0.09)	0.17* (0.10)	-0.01 (0.11)	-0.04 (0.17)	0.15 (0.16)	-0.08 (0.11)
Lecto+parents	-0.17 (0.15)	0.20** (0.08)	0.19** (0.09)	0.11 (0.08)	-0.10 (0.10)	0.05 (0.11)	0.00 (0.17)	0.05 (0.15)	-0.05 (0.12)
Lecto* Above median	0.15 (0.21)	-0.21* (0.12)	-0.24* (0.13)	-0.17 (0.13)	-0.11 (0.13)	0.04 (0.15)	-0.09 (0.22)	-0.09 (0.21)	-0.01 (0.16)
(Lecto+parents)* Above median	0.04 (0.22)	-0.10 (0.12)	-0.20 (0.13)	-0.09 (0.12)	0.02 (0.13)	-0.11 (0.15)	0.09 (0.22)	-0.11 (0.20)	-0.04 (0.17)
Lives with literate parent									
Lecto	-0.03 (0.26)	0.44*** (0.16)	0.10 (0.20)	0.31* (0.17)	0.23 (0.20)	0.04 (0.20)	-0.47 (0.32)	0.66*** (0.23)	0.37* (0.21)
Lecto+parents	-0.09 (0.27)	0.35** (0.16)	0.07 (0.18)	0.11 (0.17)	-0.10 (0.19)	-0.29* (0.16)	0.10 (0.29)	0.29 (0.22)	0.07 (0.17)
Lecto* Lives with literate parent	-0.14 (0.28)	-0.31* (0.17)	-0.05 (0.21)	-0.20 (0.18)	-0.14 (0.22)	-0.04 (0.21)	0.44 (0.34)	-0.67*** (0.25)	-0.54** (0.23)

Table A11: Heterogeneity estimates: Subconcepts - Main Specification (*continued*)

	Motor skills	Writing	Reading	Reading comprehension	Reading fluency	Phonological awareness	Listening comprehension	Ortography	Grammar
(Lecto+parents)* Lives with literate parent	-0.06	-0.23	0.00	-0.06	0.01	0.31*	-0.04	-0.34	-0.16
	(0.29)	(0.18)	(0.20)	(0.18)	(0.20)	(0.19)	(0.31)	(0.25)	(0.19)

All outcome variables are standardized. Regressions control for sex, age, baseline scores, and strata fixed effects. In case of baseline imbalances across heterogeneity subgroups, we also control for the respective imbalanced baseline variable. Standard errors are clustered at the household level. The number of observations at endline is 580. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

A4 Spillovers

Figure A2: Spillovers per Treatment Arm

Notes: Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

Figure A3: Spillovers Controlling for Class Size

Notes: Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

Figure A4: Spillovers Controlling for Average Class Ability

Notes: Average class ability is measured by 2024 national standardized test scores (“Conociendo mis logros”) at the school–grade level in 2024. These data exhibit substantial missingness (44%). Missing observations are therefore set to zero, with a missingness indicator included in the regression. Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

Figure A5: Spillovers Using Alternative Bin Definitions

Notes: For power reasons, the highest bin always pools the top 10% of the exposure distribution. Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are weighted score (left), IRT score (middle), and language grades (right).

A5 Parent Messages

Table A12: Weekly Literacy and socio-emotional learning (SEL) Activities

WeekDay	Quick summary	Category	TaRL Level	Modality	
1	1	Ask the child what letter their name starts with and search for other words that start with this letter.	Reading	Beginner + Letter	Indiv.
1	2	Tell the child positive affirmations about being smart, bright, and fast.	SEL		Indiv.
2	1	Practice recognizing and writing vowels using family names.	Writing	Beginner + Letter	Group
2	2	Ask the child to talk about what they like the most about themselves.	SEL		Indiv.
3	1	Read a text aloud to the child and search for words that start with “m” or “p”.	Reading & Oral language	Beginner + Letter	Indiv.
3	2	Tell the child they are valuable and important to others.	SEL		Indiv.
4	1	Tell the child a story about his life.	Oral language		Group
4	2	Remind the child how important they are and how much they are loved.	SEL		Indiv.
5	1	Go on a family walk and have the child name objects.	Oral language		Group
5	2	Talk about dreams and future goals.	SEL & Oral language		Indiv.
6	1	Practice tongue twisters to improve pronunciation.	Oral language	Beginner + Letter	Indiv.
6	2	Explain the importance of knowing how to read and write.	SEL		Indiv.
7	1	Create a story together using as many words starting with “b” or “c” as possible.	Oral language		Group
7	2	Explain that knowledge is like a lamp that gives light.	SEL		Indiv.

WeekDay	Quick summary	Category	TaRL Level	Modality	
8	1	Describe words to the child that they have to guess.	Oral language		Group
8	2	Talk together about family members and their strengths.	SEL		Indiv.
9	1	Practice saying simple rhymes together.	Oral language		Indiv.
9	2	Ask the child how their day at school went.	SEL & Oral language		Indiv.
10	1	Turn a notebook into a collection for newly learned words.	Writing	Word + Paragraph	Group
10	2	Explain why learning how to control impulses is important.	SEL		Indiv.
11	1	Choose three random household objects and create a story with them.	Oral language		Group
11	2	Talk about healthy habits and self-care routines.	SEL		Indiv.
12	1	Create rhymes together using simple words.	Oral language		Indiv.
12	2	Talk about rest, relaxation, and caring for mental energy.	SEL		Indiv.
13	1	Describe a favorite object and its characteristics.	Oral language		Group
13	2	Talk about commitment and how it helps achieve goals.	SEL		Indiv.
14	1	Play a game identifying animals by sounds and characteristics and talk about them.	Oral language		Group
14	2	Explain the importance of community and helping others.	SEL		Indiv.
15	1	Spell words and compare how many letters each has.	Reading	Beginner + Letter	Group
15	2	Talk about the power of writing to organize ideas and motivate the child to write down how her day went.	Oral language & Writing		Indiv.
16	1	Count syllables in place names and compare them.	Reading	Beginner + Letter	Indiv.

WeekDay	Quick summary	Category	TaRL Level	Modality
16	2	Talk about friendship, kindness, and respectful actions.	SEL	Group
17	1	Read a well-known story and invent a different ending.	Oral language	Group
17	2	Motivate writing through encouragement.	SEL	Group
18	1	Read a story based on the child's interests and discuss it.	Oral language	Indiv.
18	2	Talk about emotions and how they help us learn.	SEL	Indiv.

Figure A6: Spillovers on Parental Support at Home

Notes: Control students in the lowest exposure group (0–0.15%) serve as the reference category. Outcomes are whether parents motivate students and whether they help with school tasks (as reported by students).

A6 Semi-Structured Interviews with Teachers

Grade	Impact: T1	Impact: T2	Spillovers Control	Potential Improvements
2nd grade	<p>“Well, one of the changes was that they became more participatory, more dynamic, because the teacher [referring to NGO facilitator] used interactive activities, and that led to many changes in how they participated.”</p> <p>“Primarily in reading. They showed improved reading ability, greater word recognition, and better overall fluency.”</p>	<p><i>Teacher did not explicitly refer to parent component, just to parent sentiment towards the entire project: “... they did support it, because the parents were very happy with the project, since it was good for the children.”</i></p>	<p>“But when they returned to the classroom, the children who were attending the workshop wanted to share with the other six children, telling them about the activities they had done.”</p> <p>“... more participatory, with more targeted attention for them [the untreated students], since there were only a few students.”</p>	<p><i>No negative aspects mentioned.</i></p>
3rd grade	<p>“Yes, among the children who attended your workshop [remedial classes], at the beginning they couldn’t write some words—‘bárrafos’—and later, with the instruction they received there, you could see a change: instead of writing ‘plato’ incorrectly, they were writing ‘pato’ correctly.”</p>	<p>“... the parents were very engaged and very happy.”</p> <p>“And then the parents began to place more trust in them [the facilitators]; they attended the meetings, and the child even received a diploma at the end.”</p>	<p>“What they received in the project also helped us, because it motivated us [teachers] to work in the same way in the classroom.”</p> <p>“So, for those who didn’t all manage to get in, I had to form a small group myself and attend to them. I would set aside a few minutes—half an hour or so—for reading and writing, language.”</p> <p>“[...] and the children would share them with each other, saying, ‘Hey, do you know what? Let’s help each other and see how we’re going to do it.’”</p>	<p>“What really causes some delay is the lack of motivation among some parents, because sometimes some children did not attend.”</p>

Grade	Impact: T1	Impact: T2	Spillovers Control	Potential Improvements
4th grade	<p>“... today it’s like she lost her shyness and today she was talking [...], she writes more now and it really helped a lot with her writing.”</p> <p>“In the end, it appeared that nearly all students reached a similar level.”</p>	<p>“No, regarding that aspect, I did not hear anything.”</p>	<p>“They are slower because of their writing and reading, but thanks to God some of their classmates help them a lot as well, so in the end everything moves at roughly the same pace.”</p>	<p>“What we would improve is having more time for the program—that is, dedicating more time to it.”</p> <p>“There should be more awareness-raising among parents, encouraging them to support and motivate their children so that [...] when they are not attending, they practice more.”</p>
5th grade	<p>“They [the students] were more responsible in what they were doing, because since they were being followed up with in a different way, they were already showing learning.”</p>	<p>“Keep in mind that there are also parents who sometimes find it difficult to attend meetings. [Parental] motivation is a very important factor, and teachers and counselors also have an important role to play in reaching out to families so that parents are motivated.”</p>	<p>“They talked about it. Since they had certain classmates they felt comfortable talking to, they would share it with them.”</p>	<p>“In other words, the time is limited and it’s not every day.”</p> <p>“There should also be a bit more motivation for parents, helping them see how important it is to have these resources.”</p>
6th grade	<p>“However, I was also surprised because they [the students] improved a lot in reading as well.”</p> <p>“I was also surprised by the substantial improvement in their reading.”</p>	<p>“And communication was very effective, because they [NGO facilitators] kept us informed and included us in the [Whatsapp] group [with parents] so that we could see how they were working.”</p> <p>“There are mothers who are not able to help their children as much, and that support is important.”</p>	<p><i>Confuses control students with out-of-sample students</i></p>	<p>“... there are also parents who struggle a lot, because sometimes they are working and are not able to keep up with their children; by the time they see them at night, the children are already asleep and they can’t even help them with activities.”</p>
7th grade	<p>“They acquired knowledge; some of them, thank God, finished the year able to read, and for us that is a meaningful learning outcome.”</p>	<p>“There was support and involvement from parents in those exercises throughout the entire workshop.”</p>	<p><i>Confuses control students with out-of-sample students</i></p>	<p>“There is nothing that needs to be added or removed. Perhaps adding more hours.”</p>

A7 Literature Review

Table A13: Summary of Remedial and Literacy Interventions

Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Banerjee et al. (2007)	India	RCT; remedial education (RE) program to teach low-performing students basic literacy and numeracy skills, and a computer-assisted learning (CAL) program for maths.	RE: grade 3 and 4 students lagging behind in literacy and numeracy from ~130 schools in Mumbai and Vadodara; CAL: grade 4 students from ~150 public schools in Vadodara.	The remedial program raised average test scores by 0.28 standard deviations, with especially large gains among low-performing students, while the computer-assisted math program increased math scores by 0.47 standard deviations. Although effects persisted one year later for targeted students, they declined to about 0.10 standard deviations.	RE: The estimated impacts operate primarily through the direct treatment channel, namely the participation of students in remedial instruction, rather than through indirect spillover effects on students remaining in regular classrooms after lower-performing peers were removed.
Banerjee et al. (2010)	India	RCT; providing information (I), training community members in a new testing tool (TT), and training and organizing volunteers to hold remedial reading camps for illiterate children (RC).	I, TT: all villagers in selected villages in the state of Uttar Pradesh; RC: illiterate children in these villages (total of 280 villages).	The study finds that information and community training interventions did not increase participation in school committees, nor did they affect teacher effort or student learning within public schools. In contrast, the volunteer-based remedial reading program generated substantial engagement outside the formal school system and led to	Large- vs. small-group mechanisms: Large-group participatory institutions impose higher coordination costs and offer limited perceived efficacy. Communities are willing to invest effort in small-group, direct-action mechanisms like reading camps, but not in large-group structures such as

Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Cabezas et al. (2021)	Chile	RCT; short-term and small group (5–6 students) tutoring program using college student volunteers to increase reading outcomes among fourth grade students; report medium-term effects (8 years after intervention).	Grade 4 students from 85 schools (6,129 students).	The three-months intervention produced small short-term effects on reading outcomes. Using administrative data, the authors report a decrease in the probability of drop-out, increases in timely school progression and attendance, test scores and school grades 8 years after the intervention ended.	Tutor–student relationship (more so than tutor academic support) explains the medium-term effects.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Chimbutane et al. (2026)	Mozambique	RCT; light-touch teacher training in early-grade literacy with pedagogical materials, and teacher training plus community-level reading camps.	Grade 3 students and teachers in 160 rural public primary schools (1,596 students).	After two years of implementation, neither intervention improved teacher pedagogical knowledge or practices, nor student or teacher attendance. There were small positive effects on student reading, mainly reflected in a reduction in zero scores, with similar effects across treatment arms.	Results suggest that light-touch teacher training and complementary community literacy activities are insufficient to substantially change established teaching practices or learning outcomes; more intensive school- and/or community-based interventions appear necessary to generate meaningful gains.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Dixon et al. (2011)	India	Quasi-experimental design; use of synthetic phonics in school to increase reading and spelling attainment in English (second language).	First grade students from 20 schools in low-resource areas in Hyderabad (506 children).	This quasi-experimental study evaluates a six-month synthetic phonics intervention delivered by peripatetic teachers aimed at improving English reading and spelling among children in low-income schools in India. Compared with students receiving standard English instruction, children exposed to synthetic phonics showed statistically significant gains in both reading and spelling test scores.	Synthetic phonics improves reading and spelling by strengthening letter-sound correspondence, decoding skills, and phonological awareness, being foundational to literacy.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Duflo et al. (2020)	Ghana	RCT; assistant-led remedial pull-out lessons, assistant-led remedial after school lessons, assistant-led smaller class sizes, and teacher-implemented partial day tracking.	Students in grades 1–3 in 500 nationwide schools.	Testing different strategies—assistant teachers, smaller class sizes, additional instructional time, tracking, and remedial and differentiated instruction. Despite implementation challenges, the interventions raised test scores by about 0.1 standard deviations (or 0.4 standard deviations after adjusting for imperfect implementation), with larger gains for girls and effects persisting beyond program completion. There were no impacts on attendance, grade repetition, or dropout.	Remedial instruction is equally effective whether delivered through pull-out sessions or after-school programs; reductions in class size generate larger learning gains when instruction is targeted at remedial content rather than grade-level material; partial-day tracking does not improve average achievement beyond what is achieved through assistant-led remedial instruction.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Marinelli et al. (2024)	Colombia	Series of RCTs; remedial classes during school hours; fine-tuning the intervention tools for each subsequent cohort.	Grade 3 students from 80 public schools (2,610 students).	Assessment of the effectiveness of a reading skills intervention and its fine-tuning for struggling grade 3 students with trained teachers and structured material. The intervention had positive and persistent impacts on literacy scores and positive spillovers on some maths scores.	The effectiveness of the program increased over time due to the fine-tuning of the material and the increased dosage.
Saavedra et al. (2017)	Peru	RCT; 16 remedial sessions for science of 90 minutes during the school year.	Grade 3 students scoring in the bottom half of their science classes from 48 elementary schools in low SES areas (2,399 students).	While control group compliance was nearly perfect, treatment group compliance was 40%. Despite the low-intensity treatment, the remedial sessions increased science endline scores. Improvements are driven by boys. No spillovers to math or other students were found.	Not discussed.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Stone et al. (2019)	Latin American and the Caribbean	Systematic review; strategies to improve early grade literacy in Latin America and the Caribbean.	Studies on teacher training, nutrition, and technology-in-education programs; quantitative interventions (23 studies), qualitative interventions (6 studies), quantitative noninterventions (61 studies), qualitative noninterventions (14 studies).	Overall, the programs show no statistically significant effects on early-grade literacy. Teacher training, nutrition, and technology interventions are only effective under specific conditions, and technology-only approaches may even reduce learning outcomes.	Context-specific.

Table A14: Parenting, Caregiver, and Home-Learning Interventions

Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Amaral et al. (2024)	El Salvador	RCT; study of free digital stress management and positive parenting intervention containing information, videos, infographics and exercises.	Caregivers of children aged 0–8 (3,103 caregivers).	Intervention increased stress and anxiety and reduced caregiver–child interactions among male caregivers, while for female caregivers it had no detectable effects on mental health but reduced the use of physical violence against children.	Effects differ by sex, economic deprivation and (not) living with the partner; difficult to rule out COVID-19 pandemic influence.
Angrist et al. (2022)	Botswana	RCT; two low-technology interventions with parents to support their child’s learning during COVID-19 pandemic: SMS messages, phone calls, combined treatment.	Families with primary-school-aged children from all regions of Botswana (4,500 families).	Results demonstrate that engaging parents through simple communication technologies can effectively support learning during prolonged school disruptions. Cost-effective intervention to increase learning.	Changed parental beliefs and investments drive results.

Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Aurino and Wolf (2024)	Ghana	RCT; SMS messages to caregivers to empower them through information, reminders, and suggestions of practical, non-academic activities to engage with their children's education.	Caregivers of school-aged children across five regions of northern Ghana (2,600 caregivers, 5,000 children).	The program increased parental engagement, school participation, and children's social-emotional skills among parents with some formal schooling, but had adverse effects among parents with no schooling, reducing self-efficacy, educational aspirations, and perceived returns to schooling.	Differences in parental schooling shape how the program is received, interpreted, and internalized.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Banerji et al. (2013)	India	RCT; mother literacy and participation program with three treatment arms: adult literacy classes for mothers (ML), training for mothers on how to enhance their children's learning at home (CHAMP), a combination of the first two interventions (ML-CHAMP).	Mothers in 480 rural villages in the states of Bihar and Rajasthan (8,888 mothers).	All interventions significantly improved mothers' math and language skills, with ML and ML-CHAMP also increasing women's empowerment, and led to modest but statistically significant gains in children's math achievement. Improvements in children's language skills were observed only under the combined ML-CHAMP intervention.	Suggestive evidence that effects work through increased interest of mothers in child learning and capacity to monitor the learning.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Cortes et al. (2021)	Chile	RCT; early-childhood parenting SMS intervention varying message content and dosage (1, 3, or 5 texts per week), isolating actionable advice from information and encouragement.	Parents of four-year-old preschoolers in a district in Texas (648 parents).	Three texts per week combining information, actionable advice, and encouragement improve parenting practices more than one text per week, while increasing to five texts reduces effectiveness. Children's literacy effects are heterogeneous with respect to children's pre-treatment literacy skills.	Actionable advice is most effective when bundled with information and encouragement; children in higher quarters of the pre-treatment literacy distribution perform marginally higher with one message per week while students in lower quartiles perform worse.
Hernández-Agramonte et al. (2022)	Costa Rica	RCT; group text messages to parents of preschool students to support learning at home.	Caregivers of preschool children aged 4–5 enrolled in public schools (691 parental groups, 4,496 students).	The 15-week intervention during the COVID-19 increased cognitive skills of children whose parents received the text messages.	Increase in parental involvement in their children's development.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Kigobe et al. (2021)	Tanzania	RCT; 1-year parental involvement intervention with a teacher and parent training, focusing on communication and caregivers' involvement.	Second grade students from 24 schools in Dar es Salaam (600 students).	Treated children scored significantly higher in decoding skills, reading fluency and reading comprehension.	Not discussed.
Kim et al. (2020)	LMIC, 32 countries	Meta-analysis; review of literacy interventions in low- and middle-income countries, and their effects on children's reading skills.	(67 studies; 213,464 students).	The studied intervention differ in their approach, scope and duration. Effects range between -0.34 to 2 SD with approximately 80% of effects being positive. The largest effects were found in emergent literacy skills and the smallest effects in reading comprehension and oral language skills.	Not discussed.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Pouzevara and King (2014)	Uganda	RCT; encourage parents through their mobile phones to involve in literacy activities outside school hours with their children: SMS + audio (T1); printout of all messages and audios (T2).	Grade 1 and 2 children and their parents (~150 school children and 150 parents).	After the 91-days intervention, the intervention groups T1 and T2 showed small, significant overall improvement in literacy skills; the group that received the instructions on paper (T2) generally showed greater improvement than phone-based group (T1).	Parents in the phone-based delivery mode (T1) reported greater engagement with the activities, however, technological difficulties may explain why overall improvements were larger with the paper-based group (T2).
Ome and Menendez (2022)	Zambia	RCT; SMS messaging intervention with three weekly short stories and comprehension questions to increase reading skills + monthly parents' meetings.	Grade 2 and 3 students in Zambia's Eastern province (1,200 students).	The 9-month intervention with age appropriate and culturally relevant reading materials had positive impacts on reading skills.	Children increased their time reading at home and reading with parents.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Mateo et al. (2020)	Díaz Uruguay	RCT; behaviorally informed messages delivered via a government mobile app to increase attendance of preschool children.	Parents with children aged 3–5 enrolled in public preschools (194 schools).	The intervention had no significant average effect on preschool attendance overall, but children in the middle of the baseline absenteeism distribution and children from remote area increased attendance over the 13-week period. Also, some children development outcomes like language increased.	Easy access to information.
Mendelsohn et al. (2020)	Brazil	RCT; effects of preschool reading aloud program consisting of monthly parent workshops on parent–child interactions, home environment and child development outcomes.	Low-income families in Boa Vista (506 mother–infant dyads).	The intervention had positive impacts on parent–child interaction, cognitive stimulation, IQ, and receptive vocabulary.	Parent literacy was positively associated with reading activities but was uncorrelated to parent–child interactions, IQ and cognitive measures.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Bettinger et al. (2021)	Brazil	RCT; text messages to parents targetting information (I, information on their child's school attendance and effort) or salience (S, redirecting parents' attention without child-specific information).	Grade 9 students from 287 schools in São Paulo (19,300 students).	The intervention with weekly text messages over the school year led to significant improvements in students' test scores and grade promotion of similar magnitude for both groups (I, S). Parents in both groups become more accurate about changes (not levels) in their children's grade over time.	The results suggest that impacts are driven less by detailed belief updating and more by increased salience, which prompts parents to pay attention and independently acquire information.

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Study	Country	Study design and project design	Target population	Description and results	Mechanisms
Dizon-Ross (2019)	Malawi	RCT; simple information about their children's academic performance delivered verbally to parents.	Households with at least two enrolled children in grades 2–6 in 39 schools in the districts Machinga and Balaka (3,451 households).	Parents' baseline beliefs about children's academic performance are inaccurate. Providing parents with information about school achievements leads to belief updating and adjustments in their investments: they choose educational inputs that match their child's academic level, increase enrollment of higher-performing children and decrease the enrollment of lower-performing children.	Information provision.